

**UNIVERSITY OF LAY ADVENTISTS OF KIGALI
(UNILAK)**

**EFFECTS OF MOBILE BANKING SERVICES ON PERSONAL SAVING TRENDS OF
YOUTH IN RWANDA: A STUDY OF MOBILE BANKING AMONG UNIVERSITY OF
RWANDA STUDENTS IN HUYE CAMPUS (2021-2024)**

A Dissertation Submitted to the Faculty of Economic Science and Management in Partial
Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Award of the Master Degree of Business Administration.
Option of Finance.

BY

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Kigali, March 2025

DECLARATION

I, Jean Claude MURAGIJIMANA, affirm that this dissertation titled “**Effects of mobile banking on personal saving trends of youth in Rwanda: A study of mobile banking among university of Rwanda students in Huye campus (2021-2024)**” represents my original work. All information sources have been appropriately acknowledged through references. Furthermore, no part of this research has been submitted for a degree at this or any other university.

Jean Claude MURAGIJIMANA

Signature: _____ Date: _____

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that the dissertation titled “**Effects of mobile banking on personal saving trends of youth in Rwanda: A study of mobile banking among university of Rwanda students in Huye campus (2021-2024)**” was conducted by Jean Claude MURAGIJIMANA under my guidance and supervision and is now ready for examination.

Supervisor: Dr. Albert.O. Maake.

Signature: _____ Date: _____

DEDICATION

To the Almighty God,

**To my lovely family,
Friends and all
Academicians who
played the vital role in
my studies.**

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.

I would like to start by expressing my gratitude to God for His guidance, strength, and grace throughout this research journey. Without His blessings, this work would not have been possible. I am also profoundly thankful to the University of Lay Adventists of Kigali (UNILAK) for providing the necessary resources and an enriching academic environment that enabled me to undertake and complete this study. My sincere appreciation goes to the entire faculty and staff for their support.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

UNILAK: University of Lay Adventists of Kigali

ATM: Automated Teller Machine

USSD: Unstructured Supplementary Service Data

WB: World Bank

MLR: Multiple Linear Regression

MFS: Mobile Financial Services

UR: University of Rwanda

ICT: Information and Communication Technology

DFS: Digital Financial Services

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the effects of mobile banking services on personal saving trends of youth in Rwanda, focusing on University of Rwanda students at Huye Campus from 2021 to 2024. Specifically, the research explores how mobile banking services such as Accessibility of mobile banking services, Usage of mobile banking services, Digital financial literacy, Affordability of the services, saving accessibility, saving motivation, saving outcomes impact students' saving behaviors. A cross-sectional survey design was employed, with a sample size of 251 respondents. Questionnaire was used to collect data. The collected data was analyzed using descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, alongside multiple linear regression analysis to assess the relationship between mobile banking and students' saving patterns. The study findings confirm that mobile banking significantly influences personal savings trends among University of Rwanda students in Huye Campus, with 82.1% expressing satisfaction and 86.1% acknowledging its role in fostering frequent savings. Additionally, 78.9% agreed that mobile savings have helped them achieve financial goals, though 29.4% remained neutral or disagreed; suggesting financial progress varies due to factors like income levels and financial literacy. Challenges such as transaction fees (61.7% reported them as a barrier), security concerns (43.0% expressed distrust), financial knowledge gaps (82.0% sought more education), and poor internet connectivity (64.5% cited it as an issue) were identified. The regression analysis confirmed a significant relationship between mobile banking and saving trends, with accessibility having the strongest effect ($B = 0.34$, $p = 0.027$), followed by digital financial awareness ($B = 0.327$, $p = 0.036$), service usage ($B = 0.169$, $p = 0.015$), and affordability ($B = 0.106$, $p = 0.025$). The statistically significant constant value (1.772) suggests a baseline level of saving behavior. These findings highlight the need for improved financial literacy, expanded mobile banking access, lower transaction costs, and better connectivity to enhance financial inclusion and strengthen the savings culture among university students in Rwanda.

Keywords: Mobile banking, savings trends, Youth, University students, Rwanda.

CHAPTER ONE

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.0. Introduction.

This chapter is composed of background of the study, research problem, research objectives, research questions, and research hypotheses, significance of the study, scope of the study, conceptual framework and the definition of key terms.

1.1. Background to the study

In recent years, mobile banking has significantly transformed personal finance management among youth across different regions, including Europe, the United States, and sub-Saharan Africa. The rapid adoption of mobile banking services among young individuals has been facilitated by the widespread availability of smartphones, the development of user-friendly banking applications, and increasing financial technology innovations. In Europe, a study by ING International revealed that 50% of Europeans aged 25 to 34 used mobile banking services as early as 2013, highlighting a strong inclination towards digital financial solutions among the youth (WARC, 2013). The rise of digital investment tools, such as exchange-traded fund (ETF) savings plans, particularly in Germany, further emphasizes the shift towards mobile banking among young investors (Financial Times, 2024).

Similarly, in the United States, data from 2021 showed that approximately 74.1% of banked households with a reference person aged 15 to 24 relied on mobile banking as their primary means of accessing financial services (Statista, 2025). While mobile banking provides convenience, concerns over data security and financial literacy persist, affecting personal saving trends among young users.

In sub-Saharan Africa, mobile banking has played a crucial role in financial inclusion, particularly among the youth. The introduction of services like M-PESA in countries such as Ghana and Mozambique has enhanced accessibility to financial tools, encouraging a culture of saving (The Guardian, 2024). In the East African Community (EAC), Kenya's M-PESA, launched in 2007, revolutionized financial transactions and provided young people with efficient ways to manage

their finances and cultivate saving habits. Additionally, new mobile banking innovations such as the Fingo Africa app in Kenya and youth-targeted savings accounts in Tanzania have reinforced the growing importance of mobile banking in shaping saving trends (Capital Business, 2023).

In Rwanda, mobile banking has also significantly influenced youth saving behaviors, with platforms like MomoPay and Airtel Money enabling seamless transactions and encouraging financial discipline. A study in Rubavu District highlighted that mobile banking services, including deposits, withdrawals, and bill payments, have empowered young individuals by offering them accessible financial management tools (Ngarambe, 2016).

The necessity for research on the effects of mobile banking on personal saving trends among Rwandan youth, particularly university students, is underscored by several factors. Despite the increase of mobile banking services in Rwanda, there is limited understanding of how these services influence the saving behaviors of young individuals. A study focusing on youth in Rubavu District highlighted that mobile banking services, including money deposits, withdrawals, transfers, airtime purchases, and bill payments, have empowered young individuals by providing convenient and efficient financial management tools (Ngarambe, 2016). However, the uptake of mobile banking is still low due to limited understanding of the product and high levels of financial illiteracy (Ngarambe, 2016). This gap in knowledge is particularly pertinent for university students, who are at a critical stage of developing financial independence. Understanding the effect of mobile banking on their saving habits is essential for designing effective financial education programs and banking products tailored to this demographic.

1.2. Statement of the problem.

In Rwanda, mobile banking has become a pivotal tool for financial transactions, especially among the youth. The 2024 FinScope Survey indicates that approximately 86% of Rwandans utilized mobile money services, with 77% holding registered mobile money accounts, reflecting a significant increase from previous years (Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning [MINECOFIN], 2024). Despite this widespread adoption, there is a notable gap in understanding how mobile banking influences the personal saving behaviors of young individuals, particularly university students. Existing studies have primarily focused on the general population, leaving a

scarcity of research targeting the youth demographic, especially those in higher education institutions such as the University of Rwanda.

The absence of targeted research on university students' saving behaviors through mobile banking hinders the development of effective financial strategies and educational programs aimed at promoting prudent saving habits among young people. Ngarambe (2016) highlights that while mobile banking services in Rwanda provide convenient financial management tools, challenges such as financial illiteracy and limited savings culture persist among the youth. This study, therefore, seeks to investigate the effects of mobile banking on the personal saving trends of youth at the University of Rwanda's Huye Campus. The findings will provide valuable insights that can inform policies and financial literacy initiatives to enhance financial inclusion and foster a strong savings culture among young people in Rwanda.

1.3. Objectives of the study

The objectives of the research are with the general objective and the specific objectives.

1.3.1. General objective

The general objective of this study was to assess the effects of mobile banking on personal saving trends of youth in Rwanda.

1.3.2. Specific objectives

This research will be guided by the following specific objectives:

- i. To assess the level of mobile banking usage among University of Rwanda students in Huye Campus.
- ii. To analyze the level of personal saving trends among University of Rwanda students in Huye Campus.
- iii. To assess the challenges university of Rwanda students face when using mobile banking for personal savings.
- iv. To evaluate the effects of mobile banking usage on personal saving trends of University of Rwanda students in Huye campus.

1.4. Research questions.

This research will ask the following questions:

- i. What is the level of mobile banking usage among University of Rwanda students in Huye Campus?
- ii. What is the level of personal saving trends among University of Rwanda students in Huye Campus?
- iii. What challenges do University of Rwanda students face when using mobile banking for personal savings?
- iv. How does mobile banking usage affect the personal saving trends of University of Rwanda students in Huye Campus?

1.5. Research hypotheses.

This research will test the following hypotheses:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between mobile banking and the saving behaviors of university students.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between mobile banking and the saving behaviors of university students.

1.6. Significance of the study

This study on the effects of mobile banking on personal saving trends among youth in Rwanda, particularly University of Rwanda students at Huye Campus, is highly significant as it aligns with national and global financial policies promoting financial inclusion and digital transformation. At the national level, it supports Rwanda's Vision 2050, the National Financial Inclusion Strategy (NFIS 2022-2026), and the Smart Rwanda Master Plan (SRMP) 2020, which emphasize leveraging digital financial services to enhance economic participation and savings culture. Globally, the research aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the World Bank's Universal Financial Access (UFA) 2025 initiative, and the African Union's Agenda 2063, all of which advocate for inclusive financial systems and digital empowerment. By analyzing how mobile banking influences student savings behavior, this study provides valuable insights for policymakers, financial institutions, and development agencies, contributing to strategies that foster economic resilience, financial literacy, and sustainable development in Rwanda and beyond.

1.6.1. To the financial institutions.

Financial institutions stand to benefit significantly from the findings of this study. Understanding how mobile banking influences saving behaviors and what features resonate most with young users will enable banks and fintech companies to design more user-centric products. These innovations can drive customer acquisition and retention while promoting more robust saving habits among the youth, a demographic often underserved by traditional financial services.

1.6.2. To the youth

This study holds immense practical value. By exploring the effects of mobile banking on saving trends, it highlights how digital financial tools can empower them to manage their finances more effectively. This empowerment not only supports individual financial independence but also fosters a culture of saving, which can lead to greater economic stability and long-term prosperity.

1.6.3. To the academicians.

This study is highly significant to academicians as it contributes to the growing body of knowledge on digital financial services and youth financial behavior, particularly in the context of developing economies like Rwanda. It provides empirical evidence on how mobile banking influences personal saving trends among university students, offering valuable insights for researchers in finance, economics, and digital transformation. Additionally, the study bridges gaps in literature by focusing on young adults—an important demographic in financial inclusion discussions, thereby enriching academic debates on financial literacy, digital banking adoption, and economic empowerment. The findings can serve as a reference for future research, helping scholars explore related topics such as financial technology (fintech), behavioral economics, and digital financial education. Furthermore, universities and educators can use the study's insights to design curricula that integrate digital finance and personal money management, equipping students with practical knowledge to navigate the evolving financial landscape effectively.

1.7. Scope of the study

This study on the effects of mobile banking on personal saving trends among youth in Rwanda focuses on three key dimensions: geographical scope, content scope, and time scope.

1.7.1. Content scope.

In terms of content, the study examines how mobile banking influences students' personal saving habits, financial literacy, and money management practices. It explores key aspects such as mobile banking accessibility, and potential challenges that students face while using digital financial services. Additionally, the study evaluates the role of financial institutions and mobile service providers in shaping student saving behaviors through mobile banking platforms.

1.7.2. Geographical scope

Geographically, the study is confined to Huye Campus of the University of Rwanda, representing a population of university students who actively engage with mobile banking services. This location is significant as it offers a diverse student demographic with varying financial behaviors, making it a suitable setting to assess the effect of digital financial services on youth savings trends.

1.7.3. Time scope

Regarding the time scope, the research covers the period from 2021 to 2024, providing a contemporary analysis of mobile banking trends within this timeframe. This period captures the increasing adoption of mobile banking in Rwanda, influenced by technological advancements and government initiatives promoting financial inclusion. By focusing on these years, the study aims to reflect recent developments in digital finance and their impact on university students' saving behaviors.

1.8. Conceptual framework

According to Colander (2020) describes a conceptual framework as a flexible structure that allows researchers to make conceptual distinctions and analyze ideas systematically. It provides a foundation for understanding the phenomena under study and establishes boundaries within which the research operates. The framework also aids in interpreting results by connecting them back to the broader theoretical context. A well-designed conceptual framework is crucial in research because it clarifies variables, identifies relationships among them, and provides a rationale for the study's methodology and approach. This makes it an indispensable tool for academic inquiry and

applied research. With the review of related literature, the researcher managed to portray the sub variables by referring to the effects of mobile banking on personal saving trends of youth in Rwanda.

Figure 1 outlines the schematic presentation of the variables of concern in the study and their corresponding dimensions. The independent variable consists of Accessibility of mobile banking services, Usage of mobile banking services, Digital financial literacy, Affordability of the service while dependent variable is about personal saving trends indicators like saving accessibility, saving motivation, saving outcomes.

Figure 1.1. Conceptual framework.

Independent variable

Dependent variable

Source: Researcher compilation, 2024

1.9. Operational definition of key terms.

In any research study, clearly defining key terms is essential to ensure clarity, consistency, and a shared understanding of concepts. Operational definitions specify how each term will be measured or used within the study, eliminating ambiguity and making findings more replicable. To establish

a clear foundation for this research, it is crucial to define key terms in the context of this study, ensuring precise interpretation and application. The following section provides operational definitions of the key terms used in this research.

1.9.1. Mobile Banking services.

Mobile banking services refers to the use of mobile devices, such as smartphones or tablets, to access and manage financial services offered by a bank or financial institution. It allows users to perform various banking activities through a mobile application or web interface, providing convenience and accessibility without requiring a visit to a physical bank branch.

1.9.2. Accessibility of mobile banking services.

Accessibility of mobile banking services means the extent to which students possess the necessary digital skills and financial literacy to effectively utilize these services for saving and managing their finances.

1.9.3. Usage of Mobile Banking Service.

Usage of mobile banking services pertains to the extent to which individuals actively utilize mobile platforms for financial transactions, including checking account balances, transferring funds, paying bills, and saving money.

1.9.4. Digital Financial Literacy

Digital financial literacy involves the knowledge and skills required to effectively use digital financial services. This includes understanding how to operate mobile banking applications, recognizing the benefits and risks associated with digital financial products, and knowing how to protect oneself from digital fraud.

1.9.5. Affordability of the Service

Affordability of the service refers to the cost-effectiveness of digital financial services for users. It encompasses the fees associated with transactions, the cost of accessing the internet or mobile networks, and the price of devices needed to use these services.

1.9.6. Personal Saving Trends

Personal saving trends refer to the patterns and behaviors exhibited by individuals or households regarding the portion of their disposable income that is not consumed but set aside for future use. This includes the rate at which people save, the methods they use, and the changes in these behaviors over time.

1.9.7. Saving accessibility.

Saving accessibility refers to the ease with which individuals can save money using mobile banking services. This includes the availability of mobile savings accounts, the convenience of depositing and withdrawing savings, the affordability of transaction fees, and the flexibility of saving options.

1.9.8. Saving motivation

Saving motivation refers to the psychological, social, and economic factors that drive individuals to set aside a portion of their income for future use.

1.9.9. Saving outcomes

Saving outcomes refer to the financial results achieved from an individual's or household's saving behavior over time. These outcomes include the accumulation of wealth, financial stability, the ability to meet short-term and long-term financial goals.

1.9.10. Financial Institutions (FIs)

Financial Institutions (FIs) are Organizations such as banks, credit unions, and microfinance institutions that provide financial products and services, including mobile banking.

1.9.11. Mobile Network Operators (MNOs)

Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) are Companies that provide mobile telecommunications services, including infrastructure for mobile banking platforms.

1.9.12. Digital Financial Services (DFS)

Digital Financial Services (DFS): Financial services delivered through digital platforms, such as mobile wallets, online banking, and digital credit systems.

1.9.13. Informal Saving Methods

Informal Saving Methods are non-institutional saving practices such as saving money at home, with family, or in savings groups.

1.9.14. Economic Resilience

Economic Resilience means the ability of individuals, especially youth, to withstand and recover from financial shocks through stable saving habits and access to financial resources.

1.9.15. Rural Youth

Rural Youth are young individuals living in non-urban areas who may face unique challenges in accessing digital financial services due to geographical and infrastructural constraints.

1.9.16. Digital Divide

Digital Divide is the gap between individuals who have access to and can effectively use digital technologies and those who do not, often influenced by socioeconomic and regional factors.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0. Introduction

The literature review is a critical component of any research study, offering an in-depth exploration of relevant theories, concepts, and empirical evidence. This chapter provides a foundation for understanding the research problem and situates the current study within existing knowledge. In this study, titled effects of mobile banking services on personal saving trends of youth in Rwanda this chapter focuses on four critical areas: the theoretical review, conceptual review, empirical review, and research gap analysis.

2.1. Theoretical review

A theoretical review provides the foundation for understanding the study's key concepts and relationships by exploring relevant theories. This study examines the effects of mobile banking services on personal saving trends of youth in Rwanda through the lens of the following two theories: The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Financial Literacy Theory (Lusardi and Mitchell, 2014)

2.1.1. Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was developed by Fred Davis in 1989 to explain how users adopt and use new technology. The model identifies two key factors that influence an individual's acceptance of technology: Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU). Perceived Usefulness refers to the extent to which a person believes that using a specific technology will enhance their performance or efficiency, while Perceived Ease of Use refers to the degree to which a person finds the technology free from effort. TAM suggests that these two factors influence a user's attitude toward using technology, which in turn affects their behavioral intention and ultimately leads to actual usage.

In relation to this study on the effects of mobile banking services on personal saving trends of youth in Rwanda, TAM provides a strong framework to understand how university students in Huye Campus adopt and use mobile banking for savings. If students perceive mobile banking as useful in managing their finances and improving their saving habits, they are more likely to adopt

and use these services. Features such as quick transactions, low fees, and financial management tools can enhance their perceived usefulness. Additionally, if students find mobile banking easy to use, with user-friendly apps, convenient access, and reliable services, they will be more inclined to incorporate it into their daily financial activities.

Moreover, the behavioral intention to use mobile banking services plays a crucial role in determining the actual saving behavior of students. If they believe mobile banking is beneficial and simple to use, they are more likely to form a habit of saving through digital platforms. However, challenges such as security concerns, transaction costs, and lack of financial literacy may negatively affect their willingness to use mobile banking for savings. Understanding these perceptions can help policymakers, banks, and mobile service providers improve mobile banking services to encourage better saving habits among young people.

2.1.2. Financial Literacy Theory (Lusardi and Mitchell, 2014)

The Financial Literacy Theory was developed by Lusardi and Mitchell in 2014 to explain how financial knowledge influences individuals' ability to make informed financial decisions. The theory emphasizes that financial literacy is defined as the ability to understand and effectively use financial concepts such as saving, budgeting, and investing-plays a crucial role in financial well-being. According to this theory, individuals with higher financial literacy are more likely to engage in responsible financial behaviors, such as saving regularly, managing expenses wisely, and planning. Conversely, low financial literacy can lead to poor financial choices, debt accumulation, and financial insecurity.

With respect to this research, the Financial Literacy Theory is highly relevant in understanding how knowledge and awareness of financial concepts affects students' saving behaviors. If students at the University of Rwanda in Huye Campus have a strong understanding of financial management, they may be more likely to use mobile banking services effectively to save money. Features such as mobile wallets, automated savings, and budgeting tools can support their financial goals, but their effectiveness depends on the students' ability to make informed financial decisions.

Moreover, financial literacy influences students' confidence and trust in mobile banking. Those with higher financial knowledge may recognize the benefits of digital savings and adopt mobile

banking quickly, while those with lower financial literacy may struggle with understanding transaction fees, interest rates, and security measures, leading to limited use of mobile banking for saving. Additionally, digital financial education programs integrated with mobile banking services can help bridge knowledge gaps and encourage responsible saving habits.

2.2. Conceptual review

Mobile banking has revolutionized financial services, particularly among young people, by enhancing accessibility, affordability, and ease of use. This conceptual review explores the effects of mobile banking services on the personal saving trends of youth in Rwanda, with a focus on University of Rwanda students at Huye Campus. The study examines how key factors such as accessibility, usage, digital financial literacy, and affordability of mobile banking services— influence students' saving behaviors, including their ability to access savings, motivation to save, and overall saving outcomes. By analyzing these relationships, this review aims to provide insights into how mobile banking can promote a culture of saving among university students, ultimately contributing to financial inclusion and economic stability.

2.3.1. Mobile Banking services.

In Rwanda, mobile banking has significantly enhanced financial inclusion by providing accessible and efficient banking services to a broader population. Studies have shown that the adoption of mobile banking services has led to increased customer satisfaction, as users appreciate the convenience and security of conducting transactions via mobile platforms (Uwimana & Nyambane, 2023). Furthermore, the implementation of mobile banking has positively affected the financial performance of microfinance institutions, with evidence indicating improvements in profitability and revenue generation (Harelimana, 2017). However, challenges persist, including the need for increased customer awareness and education regarding mobile banking services to fully realize their potential benefits (Etienne, 2020).

2.3.2. Accessibility of Mobile Banking Services

Habumugisha et al. (2020) examine the accessibility of mobile banking services in Rwanda, noting that the country's widespread mobile network coverage has made financial services accessible to the majority of the population. They emphasize that youth in rural areas have particularly benefited from the availability of mobile banking agents, which has reduced the need to travel long distances to access financial services. However, the authors caution that more efforts are needed to improve digital literacy to fully leverage these services.

Manirakiza and Bizimana (2019) explore the role of financial technology companies in improving mobile banking accessibility in Rwanda. They highlight innovations such as Umurenge SACCO's digital transformation, which has enabled youth in rural communities to access banking services through mobile phones. The authors suggest that partnerships between telecom providers and financial institutions are essential to ensuring the sustainability of these services.

According to Beck et al. (2018), accessibility of mobile banking services is contingent on the availability of supportive infrastructure and user-friendly platforms. They argue that the proliferation of mobile networks in rural and urban areas has significantly bridged the gap in financial service accessibility. However, they caution that youth in low-income regions often face challenges such as high transaction costs and inadequate digital literacy, which limit their ability to access these services effectively.

Kikulwe et al. (2020) emphasize the role of mobile banking in promoting financial inclusion for youth in developing economies. Their study highlights how mobile banking services have simplified access to financial services by reducing physical and bureaucratic barriers. They note that while mobile banking has enhanced service accessibility, the lack of tailored products for youth remains a hindrance to achieving full inclusion.

2.3.3. Usage of Mobile Banking Services

Mukarugwiza and Mugisha (2020) analyze the factors influencing the usage of mobile banking services among Rwandan youth. They find that convenience, cost-effectiveness, and ease of use are key drivers of adoption. Their study also identifies peer influence and social media as critical

channels for promoting mobile banking among the youth demographic, suggesting that these platforms could be leveraged for targeted financial literacy campaigns.

Niyonteze and Karemera (2022) investigate the role of trust in the adoption of mobile banking services in Rwanda. They argue that youth are more likely to use these services when they perceive them as secure and reliable. Their findings underscore the importance of robust cybersecurity measures and transparent communication by service providers to build and maintain user trust. They recommend regular updates and user feedback mechanisms to address security concerns.

Munyegera and Matsumoto (2016) discuss the growing usage of mobile banking services among youth in East Africa, with a focus on Rwanda. They find that the adoption of mobile banking services is largely driven by the perceived ease of use and reliability of these platforms. The authors stress that financial literacy campaigns are necessary to improve usage rates, particularly among young people unfamiliar with formal banking systems.

Lwanga and Adong (2021) highlight the role of behavioral factors in influencing the usage of mobile banking services. They argue that trust in mobile banking platforms and perceived security are key determinants of adoption. Their research suggests that youth are more likely to use mobile banking services if they feel confident in the safety of their transactions. The authors recommend strengthening cybersecurity measures and promoting awareness campaigns to build trust among young users.

2.3.4. Digital Financial Literacy

Nzeyimana et al. (2019) emphasize the importance of digital financial literacy in empowering Rwandan youth to effectively use mobile banking services. They highlight that many young people lack basic knowledge of how to navigate digital financial platforms, which limits their ability to fully benefit from these services. The authors advocate for integrating digital financial literacy programs into Rwanda's educational system to bridge this knowledge gap.

Uwamahoro and Ishimwe (2021) discuss initiatives such as the "Financial Literacy Month" in Rwanda, which aim to improve financial literacy among youth. They note that these programs have significantly increased awareness and usage of mobile banking services. The authors

recommend expanding such initiatives to include practical training sessions on topics like savings, budgeting, and investment to enhance their impact.

Lusardi and Mitchell (2014) argue that digital financial literacy is a cornerstone of effective financial inclusion. They emphasize that youth need to be equipped with the skills to navigate digital platforms and understand basic financial concepts to fully utilize mobile banking services. Their research suggests that integrating financial literacy programs into school curricula can significantly improve financial decision-making among young people.

Grohmann et al. (2018) provide insights into the importance of digital financial literacy for youth empowerment. They argue that knowledge gaps in digital finance often lead to suboptimal usage of available services. Their study highlights that youth-specific training programs and public-private partnerships are essential to fostering financial literacy and ensuring sustainable financial inclusion in developing economies like Rwanda.

2.3.5. Affordability of the Service

Twizeyimana and Ndahiro (2018) explore the affordability of mobile banking services in Rwanda, noting that high transaction fees remain a barrier for many youth. They argue that competitive pricing strategies and regulatory interventions are needed to lower costs and encourage wider adoption. Their research also highlights the importance of government subsidies in making these services more affordable for low-income youth.

Mukeshimana and Kayitesi (2023) analyze the pricing models of mobile banking services in Rwanda, finding that partnerships between financial institutions and telecom providers have helped reduce costs. They discuss the introduction of low-cost packages targeting youth and suggest that further innovation in pricing strategies could enhance affordability and financial inclusion among this demographic.

Suri and Jack (2016) explore the affordability of mobile banking services and its impact on financial inclusion. They find that lower transaction costs and reduced fees associated with mobile banking are critical in encouraging adoption among low-income youth. The authors advocate for

competitive pricing strategies and subsidies to make these services more affordable for underserved populations.

Allen et al. (2016) discuss the barriers posed by high costs in mobile banking services, especially for young people in low-income settings. They highlight the role of financial institutions and policymakers in designing affordable service models. Their research underscores the importance of cost transparency and the removal of hidden fees to enhance affordability and encourage widespread adoption among youth.

2.3.6. Personal Saving Trends.

Personal saving trends among Rwandan youth have been evolving as financial literacy and access to formal financial services have improved. According to Niyomwungeri (2018), Rwandan youth are increasingly aware of the importance of saving, but their saving behavior tends to be sporadic and heavily influenced by social and economic factors. The youth in Rwanda often save in irregular patterns, typically during periods of higher income, such as after receiving seasonal agricultural yields or short-term employment. Niyomwungeri emphasizes that despite government initiatives to promote saving, including financial literacy programs, many young people remain hesitant to engage in consistent long-term saving, mainly due to low income and economic instability. Furthermore, many of the youth prioritize immediate consumption over savings, making it difficult for them to establish long-term financial security.

Personal saving trends among youth in Rwanda have shown significant changes in recent years, largely influenced by the country's development policies and the increasing use of digital financial services. According to Bannister and Taylor (2014), young people in Rwanda are becoming more conscious of their personal financial management due to increased financial literacy and access to mobile banking platforms such as M-Pesa and Airtel Money. This shift is in line with the broader trend of rising financial inclusion in Rwanda, where the national financial inclusion rate rose from 36% to 63% between 2012 and 2016 (The Reach Alliance, 2017). Youth in Rwanda are gradually adopting formal saving habits, previously uncommon in the region, as they seek more stable economic futures. However, while personal savings rates have increased, youth in Rwanda still

face challenges such as low income and high unemployment, which often hinder their ability to save consistently.

2.3.7. Saving accessibility.

According to the World Bank (2024), the accessibility of savings services in Rwanda has significantly improved, contributing to a marked increase in financial inclusion. The use of formal bank accounts for savings has grown substantially, with recent data indicating that banked populations have increased from 13% to 21%. This shift is primarily attributed to the introduction of innovative savings programs that cater to low-income individuals and rural populations, expanding access to formal financial services across the country. These changes reflect Rwanda's broader efforts to improve its financial infrastructure and promote economic development.

According to the Center for Effective Global Action (CEGA, 2020), mobile banking platforms have played a key role in enhancing savings accessibility, especially in rural and underserved areas of Rwanda. The use of mobile money services has facilitated a transition from traditional saving methods, such as informal savings groups, to more secure and accessible digital savings options. By overcoming geographic barriers, mobile money services have allowed individuals in remote areas to manage their savings without the need to travel long distances to physical bank branches. This has been particularly beneficial for women and youth, who previously faced challenges accessing formal financial services.

However, despite these advancements, challenges persist, particularly for individuals with disabilities. According to the Mastercard Foundation (2023), people with disabilities continue to face significant barriers in accessing financial services, including savings accounts. These barriers stem from a lack of assistive technology, limited financial literacy, and the physical inaccessibility of banking institutions. The report highlights the need for financial services to be more inclusive, with tailored solutions that address the unique challenges faced by individuals with disabilities. This would ensure that all members of society can participate in formal saving schemes.

Finally, Reach Alliance (2020) emphasizes the importance of financial literacy programs in improving the accessibility and effective use of savings services in Rwanda. The organization's research shows that while access to savings accounts has improved, a lack of financial education

prevents many individuals from fully utilizing these services. In particular, low financial literacy rates among rural populations and youth hinder their ability to make informed decisions about saving and managing money. The Reach Alliance advocates for targeted financial literacy initiatives to empower these groups, thereby promoting long-term financial security and contributing to the country's economic development.

2.3.8. Saving motivation

According to the World Bank (2024), motivating Rwandans to save has become a priority for economic growth and financial stability. The country has experienced a remarkable increase in the use of formal savings accounts, particularly among rural populations, driven by initiatives such as mobile banking and innovative savings programs. This increase in savings is viewed as critical for unlocking Rwanda's private sector potential and securing long-term economic sustainability. Programs targeting financial education and saving behavior have become pivotal in encouraging Rwandans to shift from informal to formal savings methods.

According to Minecofin (2019), the Rwandan government has been a significant proponent of cultivating a savings culture. Through national campaigns and government-backed savings schemes, Rwandans have been urged to adopt saving habits that will not only benefit their households but also contribute to the national economy. The Minister of Finance and Economic Planning, Dr. Uzziel Ndagijimana, emphasized that widespread saving behaviors are necessary to promote financial security and economic stability in the country. The government's focus on saving motivation has been crucial in building a foundation for long-term economic growth.

However, Kura (2023) highlights that saving motivation remains low among Rwandan youth, with only 13% participating in long-term savings programs such as Ejo Heza. While many youth recognize the importance of saving, the lack of financial literacy and limited access to appropriate savings tools have hindered them from engaging more fully with formal savings mechanisms. To increase saving motivation among this group, Kura suggests that financial education programs need to be more accessible and tailored to younger audiences, helping them understand the benefits of saving for the future.

World Relief (2012) emphasizes the role of community-based financial education programs in motivating individuals to save. Their Savings for Life program has been instrumental in providing financial education and accessible savings options to Rwanda's poorest populations, many of whom have never before had access to formal banking services. By offering these services through local churches and community groups, the program helps instill the habit of saving and empowers individuals to take control of their financial futures, demonstrating the power of community-driven initiatives to motivate saving behaviors.

2.3.9. Saving outcomes.

According to the World Bank (2024), the expansion of formal savings mechanisms in Rwanda has led to significant financial stability and economic development. The percentage of adults saving through formal bank accounts has increased from 13% to 21%, reflecting a shift from informal to secure banking institutions. This transition has enhanced financial inclusion, allowing individuals to accumulate assets, manage financial risks, and improve their overall economic well-being. The increase in formal savings is also seen as a key driver of investment and business growth in Rwanda.

According to Maniriho, Musabanganji, and Lebailly (2020), increased household savings have a direct and measurable impact on Rwanda's economic growth. Their study found that a 1% increase in national savings is correlated with a 3.29% rise in the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). This highlights the role of savings in mobilizing domestic resources for investment, reducing dependency on foreign aid, and fostering sustainable economic progress. The researchers emphasize that policies encouraging savings, particularly in rural areas, can be instrumental in accelerating Rwanda's economic development.

According to Uwizeyimana and Mbabazi (2023), community-based savings groups, locally known as "Ibimina," have contributed significantly to improving household economic resilience. Their study found that participation in these savings groups has led to increased household incomes, better access to microloans, and greater investment in small businesses and agricultural activities. Members of these groups reported an improvement in their overall financial security, as collective saving mechanisms allowed them to access funds for emergencies, education, and business

expansion. This demonstrates that informal savings structures remain crucial for economic empowerment, particularly in rural communities.

According to Nkurunziza (2023), long-term savings schemes like the Ejo Heza program have played a critical role in promoting financial security, particularly among vulnerable populations. His study on young people living with HIV in Rwanda found that those enrolled in the Ejo Heza program exhibited improved financial literacy and a stronger saving culture. This resulted in better financial independence and improved welfare outcomes, demonstrating the importance of targeted savings programs in addressing the needs of marginalized groups. The success of such initiatives underscores the broader impact of structured saving mechanisms in fostering inclusive economic growth.

2.4. Empirical review.

An empirical review focuses on summarizing and analyzing existing studies and data relevant to the research topic. For the study titled effects of mobile banking services on personal saving trends of youth in Rwanda, it is essential to examine findings from prior studies, surveys, and reports on mobile banking services, and youth saving behaviors in similar contexts. This review discusses how mobile banking services affects savings, particularly among youth, referencing empirical insights from different perspectives.

According to Shree, Gurusamy, and Balaji (2019), their study titled Perception of youth towards mobile banking usage intention: An empirical study, sought to explore the behavior and usage intentions of youth customers toward mobile banking in Chennai, India. The researchers adopted a descriptive research design with a quantitative approach, using structured questionnaires to collect data from 109 respondents selected through purposive sampling. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential analysis to evaluate factors influencing mobile banking usage intentions. The key findings revealed that convenience, safety, and trust are critical in shaping the mobile banking usage intentions of young individuals. The study highlighted that a positive perception of these factors is associated with a higher likelihood of adopting mobile banking services, which can facilitate better personal savings management among youth (Shree et al., 2019).

According to Loaba (2021), in the study titled the impact of mobile banking services on saving behavior in West Africa, the objective was to examine how mobile banking services affect individual saving behaviors in West African countries. The study employed an empirical analysis using cross-sectional data sourced from national financial inclusion surveys and the Global Findex database. Econometric techniques were applied to analyze the impact of mobile banking on savings. The findings indicated that mobile banking services positively influence both the propensity to save and the amount saved by individuals. This underscores the crucial role of digital financial services in promoting savings and improving financial security in the region, particularly among individuals with limited access to traditional banking services.

According to Ouma, Odongo, and Were (2017), in their study titled Mobile financial services and financial inclusion: Is it a boon for savings mobilization?, the researchers aimed to investigate the impact of mobile financial services on the likelihood of saving and the amount saved by individuals in Africa. The study employed a quantitative research design using cross-sectional data from the World Bank's Global Findex database. Econometric modeling techniques were used to analyze the relationship between mobile financial services usage and savings behavior. The key findings revealed that mobile financial services significantly increase both the likelihood of individuals saving and the amounts saved. This indicates that mobile banking serves as a catalyst for financial inclusion and savings mobilization across Africa.

According to Isaboke and Ukwimanishaka (2017), their study titled Mobile banking services empowering youth in Rwanda: A case of Gisenyi sector of Rubavu District, sought to assess the role of mobile banking services in empowering youth financially. The researchers adopted a descriptive survey design and collected data using structured questionnaires administered to a sample of youth in the Gisenyi sector of Rwanda's Rubavu District. Data analysis was performed using descriptive statistics, including frequency distributions and percentages. The findings revealed that mobile banking services have significantly empowered the youth by providing them with accessible financial services. As a result, youth have developed better saving habits and improved their financial management skills, demonstrating the positive influence of mobile banking on financial empowerment in Rwanda.

2.4. Research Gap analysis.

While existing studies have explored mobile banking adoption and financial behavior, they lack a specific focus on the youth demographic in Rwanda, particularly university students. Shree, Gurusamy, and Balaji (2019) examined mobile banking adoption among youth in India, identifying factors like convenience, safety, and trust as key determinants. However, their study did not analyze how these factors translate into actual saving behaviors. This gap is critical for understanding whether mobile banking services in Rwanda are merely being adopted for transactional convenience or if they are effectively influencing youth saving trends.

Loaba (2021) provided insights into the relationship between mobile banking and savings in West Africa but relied on secondary data without examining youth as a distinct financial group. This creates a gap in understanding how mobile banking services directly influence the saving patterns of young people, particularly students who may have limited and irregular income sources. The current study on University of Rwanda students in Huye Campus will address this gap by focusing on a specific youth segment that heavily interacts with digital financial services and may have unique saving behaviors influenced by their educational and financial circumstances.

Ouma, Odongo, and Were (2017) confirmed that mobile financial services enhance savings across Africa but did not provide country-specific insights, making it difficult to apply their findings directly to Rwanda. The regulatory and digital infrastructure differences across African nations suggest that Rwanda's financial ecosystem requires localized studies. The present study on University of Rwanda students in Huye Campus will fill this gap by examining how mobile banking services—considering factors like accessibility, usage, digital financial literacy, and affordability—specifically affect personal saving trends among Rwandan youth. This localized perspective will provide insights relevant to policymakers and financial institutions seeking to improve youth financial inclusion.

Lastly, while Isaboke and Ukwimanishaka (2017) explored mobile banking's impact on youth in Rwanda, their study was geographically limited to the Gisenyi sector of Rubavu District and relied on descriptive statistics rather than econometric analysis. Their findings suggest that mobile banking services enhance financial empowerment, but the study lacked a broad analytical framework to establish causal relationships between mobile banking usage and saving behaviors. The proposed research at the University of Rwanda's Huye Campus will address this limitation.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.0. Introduction

This chapter outlines the research methodology employed to explore the effects of mobile banking on personal saving trends among the youth in Rwanda, with a specific focus on students at the University of Rwanda's Huye Campus. The study aims to understand how mobile banking influences saving behaviors and the underlying factors that shape these trends among young people who are increasingly reliant on digital financial platforms. To achieve this objective, the research adopts a systematic approach, detailing Profile of the Study, Research Design, Sampling Design, Data Sources, Data Instruments, Validity and Reliability, Data Processing, Data Analysis, Limitations of the Study and Ethical consideration.

3.1. Profile of the study

This study examines the effects of mobile banking on personal saving trends among youth in Rwanda, focusing on students residing in hostels at the University of Rwanda – Huye Campus. The research specifically targets students from the College of Arts and Social Sciences (CASS), located in Huye District, Southern Province. Out of the total CASS student population of 3,378, approximately 676 students (20%) live in hostels, making them the primary respondents of this study. By concentrating on hostel residents, the research aims to analyze how mobile banking services influence their saving behaviors. Given that hostel students often manage their finances independently, they provide a relevant sample for understanding mobile banking's impact on personal savings. This focus will offer valuable insights into how mobile banking facilitates financial management and savings among young people in Rwanda.

3.2. Research Design

This study adopts a cross-sectional survey design with a quantitative approach to investigate the effects of mobile banking on personal saving trends among youth in Rwanda, specifically focusing on students residing in hostels at the University of Rwanda's Huye Campus. The cross-sectional survey design is chosen to collect data at a single point in time, allowing for an analysis of the relationship between mobile banking usages and saving behaviors among the target population.

By employing a quantitative approach, the study aims to collect and analyze numerical data to provide an objective assessment of these relationships. According to Creswell (2014), cross-sectional surveys are effective for systematically examining social phenomena by capturing data from a large sample within a specific timeframe. This study will utilize structured questionnaires to collect standardized information, enabling statistical analysis and the identification of patterns and correlations between key variables. The findings will offer insights into how mobile banking influences the saving behaviors of university students in Rwanda.

3.3. Sampling design

A sampling design refers to the strategic framework or methodology used to select a subset of individuals or units from a larger population to participate in a research study. This design determines how the sample is drawn and ensures that it is representative of the population to achieve accurate and reliable results. According to Singh and Masuku (2014), a sampling design encompasses the population definition, sampling technique, and sample size, which collectively influence the validity of the research outcomes. A well-constructed sampling design minimizes bias, optimizes resource use, and enhances the generalizability of findings.

3.3.1. Population of the study.

The population refers to the entire group of individuals that the researcher intends to study and draw conclusions from (Creswell, 2014). The population of this study includes youth students aged 20 to 35 enrolled in the College of Arts and Social Sciences (CASS) at the University of Rwanda-Huye Campus. This demographic group is chosen because youth constitute a significant proportion of Rwanda's population and are particularly responsive to advancements in digital technology, including mobile banking platforms (National Institute of Statistics of Rwanda [NISR], 2022). The youth segment is also pivotal for fostering a culture of savings, which is essential for long-term financial inclusion and economic growth (World Bank, 2021).

The following table describes the distribution of students across the different schools within the College of Arts and Social Sciences (CASS) at the University of Rwanda -Huye Campus. It also shows the number of students living in hostels, which constitutes 20% of the total student population and will be the major respondents for this study.

Table 3.1: Population of the study.

Faculty	Number of students	Students Living in Hostels
School of Arts and languages	675	135
School of Social, political and administrative sciences	1,014	203
School of Journalism and communication	507	101
School of philosophy and Religious studies	507	68
School of governance and development studies	844	169
Total	3378	676

3.3.2. Sample size determination

To determine the appropriate sample size for this study, Slovin's formula was used, this formula is commonly applied when the total population is known, and the researcher wants to determine a

representative sample with a given margin of error. The formula is expressed as:
$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where:

n = Sample size

N = Population size (676 in this case)

e= Margin of error (commonly 0.05 or 5%)

For **e=0.05 (5% margin of error):**

$$n = \frac{676}{1 + 676(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{676}{1 + 676(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{676}{1 + 1.69}$$

$$n = \frac{676}{2.69}$$

$$n \approx 251$$

Therefore, the study will focus on a sample of 251 students who live in hostels, ensuring that the results are statistically representative of this particular group at the University of Rwanda – Huye Campus. This table provides a clear breakdown of the sample size determination process:

Table 3.2: Sample size.

Faculty	Students Living in Hostels	% of sampled students from those living in hostels	Sampled students
School of Arts and languages	135	19.97%	50
School of Social, political and administrative sciences	203	30%	75
School of Journalism and communication	101	14.94%	38
School of philosophy and Religious studies	68	10.06%	25
School of governance and development studies	169	25%	63
Total	676	100 %	251

3.3.3. Sampling technique.

In this study, stratified random sampling will be employed alongside simple random sampling to ensure that the sample accurately represents the population of students who live in hostels at the University of Rwanda – Huye Campus. Stratified random sampling is a probability sampling technique where the population is divided into distinct subgroups (strata) based on a shared characteristic—in this case, the students' schools of study. The strata will include the School of Arts and Languages, School of Social, Political and Administrative Sciences, School of Journalism and Communication, School of Philosophy and Religious Studies, and School of Governance and Development Studies. From each stratum, a proportional number of respondents will be selected using simple random sampling, ensuring representation across all schools (Creswell & Creswell, 2017). This approach minimizes sampling error and enhances the precision of the study by accounting for variability within the hostel population.

To implement this technique, a comprehensive list of all students living in hostels will be compiled, with the population divided into strata based on their respective schools. Each student within a stratum will be assigned a unique identification number. A random number generator will then be used to select 251 students proportionally from the strata (Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2017). This ensures both equal opportunity for selection within each subgroup and an unbiased representation of the overall hostel population.

By combining stratified random sampling with simple random sampling, the study aims to ensure that the final sample not only reflects the diversity of students living in hostels but also allows for more nuanced insights into the effects of mobile banking on saving trends and behaviors among students from different academic backgrounds. The use of these complementary methods will enhance the reliability, validity, and generalizability of the study's findings (Fink, 2017).

3.4. Data Sources.

In this study, primary data will be collected through a questionnaire to explore the effects of mobile banking on personal saving trends among university students at the University of Rwanda – Huye Campus.

Primary Data: The primary data will be gathered directly from the respondents (university students) through a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire will be administered to students living in hostels, who represent 20% of the total student population at the campus. This group of students is expected to provide direct insights into their experiences and perceptions of mobile banking services, as well as their saving behaviors. The survey will collect data on various factors, including mobile banking accessibility, usage, frequency, affordability, and digital financial literacy, as well as personal saving trends, such as saving accessibility, saving motivation, saving outcomes. The primary data will serve as the foundation for analyzing the direct effects of mobile banking on students' personal savings.

The use of primary data will ensure a comprehensive understanding of the effects of mobile banking on personal saving trends among university students in Rwanda. The primary data will provide specific insights into the student population,

3.5. Data collection instruments.

During the study, the researcher will use structured questionnaire as data collection technique.

3.5.1. Structured questionnaire.

The study utilized a structured questionnaire as the primary data collection method. This pre-designed questionnaire comprised closed-ended questions, allowing respondents to select from predetermined answer choices. The structured approach was chosen due to its multiple benefits, which enhance the efficiency and reliability of data collection.

One of the key advantages of employing a structured questionnaire is its efficiency, as it enables the researcher to gather data from numerous respondents simultaneously. Additionally, the predefined response options simplify data analysis, ensuring a systematic and organized evaluation process. This method is also easy to administer, particularly among literate participants, making the study process more accessible and convenient.

To design the questionnaire, the researcher incorporated a Likert scale to assess participants' perspectives on key aspects of mobile banking services. The same scale was also applied to

evaluate factors influencing personal saving trends. The Likert scale provided five response options: 5 – Strongly agree, 4 – Agree, 3 – Neutral, 2 – Disagree, 1 – Strongly disagree.

3.6. Validity and Reliability.

Validity in this study ensures that the research instrument accurately measures the concepts of mobile banking services and personal saving trends among youth in Huye District. The content validity was established by seeking expert feedback on the questionnaire to confirm that the items comprehensively represent key dimensions of mobile banking services (e.g. Accessibility of mobile banking services, Usage of mobile banking services, Digital financial literacy, Affordability of the service) and saving trends (e.g. Saving accessibility, saving motivation, saving outcomes) reviewed the questionnaire. Construct validity was established by aligning the questionnaire with theoretical frameworks and empirical studies on digital financial inclusion and saving behavior (Heale & Twycross, 2015).

Reliability refers to the consistency of the questionnaire in producing stable and consistent results. This was tested using Cronbach’s Alpha coefficients, with a value above 0.7 indicating acceptable internal consistency (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011). Below is the reliability analysis for the study's variables:

Table 3.3. Reliability Results

Variables	Number of Items	Cronbach’s Alpha Coefficient
Independent Variables		
Accessibility of mobile banking services.	5	0.82
Usage of mobile banking services	6	0.85
Digital financial literacy	4	0.79
Affordability of the service	3	0.76
Dependent Variables		
Saving accessibility	4	0.81
Saving motivation	3	0.78
Saving outcomes	5	0.83

3.7. Data processing and analysis.

Raw data was transformed into meaningful interpreted report using different techniques. In order to get quality information, there is generally need for standard checking so that the researcher could end up with realistic data, which clearly reflect the depicted situation. Thus, standard checking is done through editing, coding, and tabulation. This is done in order to reduce detailed data to manageable proportions.

3.7.1. Data processing

a. Editing

In editing the researcher scrutinized and verified the questionnaires in order to avoid errors and repetitions". Once this type of data processing is made, the analysis becomes simple and easy to the researcher.

b. Coding

The researcher will summarize data by classifying the different responses given into categories for easy interpretation by assigning a symbol or a number to a response for identification purposes.

c. Tabulation

Tabulation means putting data in some kinds of statistical tables through which the number of occurrence of responses to a particular question is shown. These tables are constructed in such way that frequency of responses to a particular question is presented. It is also presented in percentages.

3.8. Data analysis and interpretation.

In this study, the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) will be used for data processing and analysis, facilitating the presentation, interpretation, and discussion of findings. The analysis will be structured around the research objectives, with the choice of statistical techniques depending on the nature of the problem and the type of data collected.

3.8.1. Descriptive Statistics.

Descriptive statistics will help understand the general trends in mobile banking usage and saving behavior. The key statistical measures will include the mean, standard deviation of responses. These statistics will provide insights into how frequently students engage with mobile banking and how their saving behaviors vary.

Mean (Arithmetic Mean)

The mean measures the central tendency of the collected responses and is calculated as:

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum X_i}{N}$$

Where:

\bar{X} = Mean (average value)

X_i = Individual data points (e.g., mobile banking transactions per year)

N = Total number of responses

Standard Deviation (Measure of Dispersion)

The standard deviation (σ) measures the variability in responses and is calculated using the formula:

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum (X_i - \bar{X})^2}{N}}$$

Where:

σ = Standard deviation

X_i = Individual data points

\bar{x} = Mean

N= Total number of observations

In this study on the effects of mobile banking on personal saving trends among University of Rwanda students in Huye Campus, the arithmetic mean and standard deviation will be crucial in analyzing and interpreting the collected data. These two descriptive statistical measures will help summarize the dataset, identify patterns, and assess variations in students' experiences with mobile banking and savings.

A five-point Likert scale will be used to measure students' perceptions of mobile banking and personal savings. The scale consists of 1 (Strongly Disagree), 2 (Disagree), 3 (Neutral), 4 (Agree), and 5 (Strongly Agree). The inclusion of a neutral midpoint allows respondents to express indifference or uncertainty, which provides a more balanced view of their perceptions regarding mobile banking usage, affordability, financial literacy, and saving behavior.

The arithmetic mean will summarize the overall trend of responses. A high mean, closer to 5 (e.g., above 4.0), will indicate that most students agree or strongly agree with a particular statement, such as mobile banking being accessible, affordable, or motivating them to save. A low mean, closer to 1 (e.g., below 2.0), will suggest that most students disagree or strongly disagree, indicating negative perceptions or limited adoption of mobile banking for savings. A mean around 3.0 suggests a neutral stance, meaning students neither strongly agree nor disagree, which may indicate uncertainty or mixed experiences.

The standard deviation will measure the level of agreement or variability in responses. A low standard deviation (e.g., ≤ 0.8) means that most students share similar opinions, showing a strong consensus in their perception of mobile banking services. A high standard deviation (e.g., ≥ 1.2) suggests significant variability, meaning students have differing views and experiences. For example, if the mean affordability rating is 4.3 with a standard deviation of 0.5, it would indicate that most students find mobile banking affordable, with little disagreement. However, if the mean is 3.0 with a standard deviation of 1.5, it suggests that opinions on affordability are highly varied, possibly due to differences in financial situations or transaction costs.

By analyzing these statistical measures, this study will determine whether mobile banking has a consistent or varying impact on students' saving behaviors. It will also help identify areas where

interventions, such as financial literacy programs or service improvements, may be needed to enhance students' mobile banking experiences in Rwanda.

3.8.2.1. Spearman's Rank Correlation Analysis

To determine the relationship between mobile banking and personal saving behavior, this study will use Spearman's Rank Correlation Analysis. This method measures the strength and direction of the association between ranked variables, making it suitable for analyzing ordinal data such as survey responses on mobile banking usage and saving behavior.

Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient (ρ) is computed using the formula:

$$\rho = 1 - \frac{6 \sum d_i^2}{n(n^2 - 1)}$$

Where:

ρ = Spearman's rank correlation coefficient

d_i = Difference between the ranks of paired observations

n = Number of observations

Interpretation of Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficients

The correlation coefficient (ρ) ranges from **-1 to +1** and will be interpreted as follows:

$\rho=+1$ → Perfect positive correlation (higher values of one variable correspond to higher values of the other).

$\rho=-1$ → Perfect negative correlation (higher values of one variable correspond to lower values of the other).

$\rho=0$ → No correlation between the variables.

By applying Spearman's Rank Correlation analysis, this study will assess how mobile banking factors influence personal saving behavior factors among university students in Rwanda. The results will provide insights into whether accessibility, usage, financial literacy, and affordability have a meaningful impact on students' ability to save money using mobile banking services.

3.8.2.2. Regression Analysis

A Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) model will be used to determine the relationship between mobile banking and personal saving behavior. The general regression equation is:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \epsilon \text{ Where:}$$

Y = Saving Behavior (measured by Saving Accessibility, Saving Motivation, and Saving Outcomes)

X₁ = Mobile Banking Accessibility

X₂ = Usage of Mobile Banking Services

X₃ = Digital Financial Awareness

X₄ = Affordability of Mobile Banking Services

β₀ = Intercept

β₁, β₂, β₃, β₄ = Regression Coefficients representing the effect of independent variables on saving behavior
ε = Error term

Each coefficient β represents the expected change in saving behavior for a one-unit increase in the respective independent variable, assuming all other variables remain constant.

Interpretation of Possible Coefficients

β₁ (Accessibility of Mobile Banking Services): If β_1 is positive and significant, it means that higher accessibility to mobile banking services increases saving behavior. A possible reason could be that when banking services are easily accessible, students find it more convenient to save money digitally rather than using traditional methods.

β_2 (Usage of Mobile Banking Services): A positive and significant β_2 indicates that frequent use of mobile banking leads to better saving habits. Students who actively engage in mobile transactions may develop disciplined saving behavior through automated savings features or digital tracking.

β_3 (Digital Financial Literacy): If β_3 is positive and significant, it suggests that students with higher financial literacy are more likely to save effectively using mobile banking. Financially literate students might have better knowledge of interest rates, investment opportunities, and digital financial tools that encourage saving.

β_4 (Affordability of Mobile Banking Services): If β_4 is negative or insignificant, it could indicate that affordability is not a major factor influencing saving behavior. However, if it is positive and significant, it means that students who perceive mobile banking as affordable are more likely to use it for saving purposes.

3.9. Limitations of the study.

Despite its strengths, this study on the effects of mobile banking on personal saving trends among youth in Rwanda, focusing on University of Rwanda students in Huye Campus (2021–2024), is subject to several limitations that may influence the findings and their applicability.

A primary limitation is the geographical focus on Huye Campus, which, while allowing for an in-depth analysis of mobile banking usage among university students, may not fully represent the broader trends across Rwanda. Financial infrastructure, socioeconomic conditions, and cultural attitudes toward savings vary across different regions, potentially limiting the generalizability of the findings. Youth in urban areas with better digital access may exhibit different saving behaviors compared to those in rural settings with limited banking services.

The reliance on self-reported data presents another challenge. Data collected through questionnaires may be subject to recall bias or social desirability bias, where respondents provide answers they perceive as more socially acceptable rather than completely accurate. This could affect the reliability of responses related to mobile banking usage, saving motivation, and financial literacy.

Furthermore, technological and digital literacy barriers could affect the study results. Some students may struggle with using mobile banking due to limited financial literacy, lack of smartphones, or unreliable internet access. This could lead to an overrepresentation of students who are already financially and digitally included, while excluding perspectives from those with limited access to mobile banking services.

Additionally, external factors such as inflation, employment status, and cultural norms regarding saving may independently influence students' saving behaviors, potentially interacting with or overshadowing the specific effects of mobile banking. For instance, fluctuating economic conditions or students' access to part-time jobs may play a significant role in determining their ability to save, beyond the availability of mobile banking services.

While these limitations should be acknowledged, they do not invalidate the study's findings. Instead, they highlight areas for future research, such as expanding the study to include students from multiple campuses across Rwanda or integrating qualitative methods to gain deeper insights into personal saving behaviors and mobile banking challenges.

3.10. Ethical consideration

The researcher will comply with ethical procedures to protect the rights of the research participants, involving the principle of voluntary participation, which requires that participants do not need to be pressured into participating in this research. The following ethical measures were adhered to: Right of the participant, in this study, no attempt was made to harm participants deliberately and those who could experience any form of harm be it through victimization, emotional or otherwise, was informed in advance of their right to withdraw from participating in the study.

Confidentiality and anonymity, Confidentiality means that information from participants was not going to be spread to the public nor made available to colleagues, subordinates or superiors. In this study, all information about participants was treated with confidentiality and the participants were anonymous. A covering letter also assured respondents that all responses would be treated with utmost confidentiality and anonymity.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, INTERPRETATION, FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS.

4.0. Introduction

This chapter contains data presentation, interpretation and analysis. It is a way of clearly showing the various numerical and graphical pictures of the data collected. The data are interpreted by giving a meaning for readers to clearly understand the information being presented. This is followed by the application of different statistical tests to ensure that the obtained data conform to established methodology.

4.1. Data presentation

The analysis will begin with Descriptive Statistics, where an overview of the demographic distribution of respondents (gender, age, employment status, and education level) will help contextualize the sample's characteristics. Measures of central tendency (mean) and dispersion (standard deviation) will summarize data on mobile banking usage, accessibility, affordability, and saving behaviors, revealing key patterns and trends within the dataset. Following this, Correlation Analysis will assess the relationships between key variables such as mobile banking accessibility and saving behavior using Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficients, and statistical significance will be determined through p-values.

Next, Multiple Linear Regression will identify the predictors of saving behavior, evaluating how factors like accessibility, usage, affordability, and financial literacy influence saving outcomes. Hypothesis Testing (ANOVA) will assess if differences in mobile banking usage relate to varying saving behaviors. The analysis will also explore Challenges and Limitations, highlighting barriers such as transaction fees, security concerns, and internet connectivity issues. Finally, the Conclusion and Recommendations will synthesize insights from the analysis, offering recommendations for improving mobile banking services and promoting financial literacy to foster better saving habits.

Table 4.1. Demographic Distribution of Respondents

Category	Variable	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Gender Distribution	Female	66	26.3%
	Male	185	73.7%
	Total	251	100.0%
Employment Status	Full-time	35	13.9%
	Paid employment	64	25.5%
	Part-time	17	6.8%
	Self-employment	43	17.1%
	Unemployed	86	34.3%
	Total	251	100.0%
Age Distribution	18-24 years	123	49.0%
	25-29 years	81	32.3%
	30-35 years	42	16.7%
	Total	251	100.0%
Education Level	Post-graduate	32	12.7%
	Undergraduate	216	86.1%
	Total	251	100.0%

Source: Primary data, 2025.

The gender distribution of the study reveals that out of 251 respondents, **66 (26.3%)** are female, while **185 (73.7%)** are male. This indicates that the sample is predominantly male, which may reflect the actual gender composition of the target population. The notable gender gap suggests that men may have had greater accessibility or willingness to participate in the study compared to women.

In terms of employment status, the data shows that 86 (34.3%) of the respondents are unemployed, making up the largest proportion of the sample. This is followed by 64 (25.5%) who are engaged in paid employment, 43 (17.1%) in self-employment, 35 (13.9%) in full-time employment, and 17 (6.8%) in part-time employment. The significant number of unemployed individuals suggests a possible challenge in job availability or workforce integration among the respondents. The relatively high proportion of self-employed individuals (17.1%) may indicate entrepreneurial tendencies or a lack of formal employment opportunities.

The age distribution data highlights that the majority of respondents are relatively young, with 123 (49.0%) falling within the 18-24 years age range, followed by 81 (32.3%) aged 25-29 years, and 42 (16.7%) aged 30-35 years. The dominance of younger individuals in the sample suggests that the study primarily represents a youthful demographic, which could have implications for financial behavior, employment trends, and educational attainment.

Regarding education level, a significant majority of the respondents, 216 (86.1%), are undergraduate students or degree holders, while 32 (12.7%) have attained postgraduate education. This distribution suggests that most participants are in the process of obtaining or have recently completed their first degree, with only a small fraction pursuing advanced studies. The high percentage of undergraduate respondents aligns with the young age distribution, reinforcing the idea that many individuals in the sample are still in the early stages of career development.

Overall, the demographic profile of the study indicates a predominantly male, young, and highly educated population, with a considerable proportion facing employment challenges. These findings provide essential context for understanding the broader implications of the study, particularly in relation to financial behavior, employment trends, and economic participation.

4.2. Data analysis, Interpretations, findings and discussions

4.2.1. Descriptive statistics

Table 4.2. Accessibility of Mobile Banking Services

Category	Variable	N	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)
1. Accessibility of Mobile Banking Services	It is easy to open a mobile banking account.	251	3.7418	0.55055
	Mobile banking services are easily accessible on my mobile device.	251	4.2249	0.74435
	There are sufficient mobile banking agents and ATMs near my location.	251	4.1230	0.75988
	I do not have trouble when accessing my mobile banking account.	251	3.7521	0.97967
	I can easily perform transactions anytime and anywhere.	251	4.1545	0.66434

The findings indicate a generally high level of accessibility to mobile banking services among students at the University of Rwanda, Huye Campus. The highest mean score ($M = 4.22$, $SD = 0.74$) suggests that students find mobile banking services easily accessible on their mobile devices. Similarly, the ease of performing transactions anytime and anywhere ($M = 4.15$, $SD = 0.66$) and the availability of sufficient mobile banking agents and ATMs ($M = 4.12$, $SD = 0.76$) indicate strong infrastructural support for mobile banking. However, the ease of opening a mobile banking account ($M = 3.74$, $SD = 0.55$) and the ability to access the account without trouble ($M = 3.75$, $SD = 0.98$) scored slightly lower, indicating that while accessibility is generally high, some challenges remain.

The findings align with prior research on mobile banking accessibility in developing economies. Studies have shown that mobile banking infrastructure significantly influences financial inclusion (Demirgüç-Kunt et al., 2018). The high accessibility reported in this study suggests that mobile banking has reached a level where it can significantly contribute to personal saving trends among youth. However, the relatively lower score on ease of account opening indicates a potential barrier to initial adoption, similar to findings by Jack and Suri (2016), who highlighted bureaucratic and technical challenges in mobile banking registration.

The accessibility of mobile banking services plays a crucial role in shaping the saving behaviors of young individuals. The ease of accessing mobile banking services and performing transactions suggests that students at the University of Rwanda, Huye Campus, are in a favorable position to leverage mobile banking for savings. Prior research by Mbiti and Weil (2016) found that increased mobile banking accessibility leads to higher financial participation and improved saving habits. This aligns with the findings of this study, indicating that the more accessible mobile banking services are, the more likely students are to develop positive saving behaviors. However, challenges related to account opening and occasional accessibility difficulties may hinder full utilization, suggesting the need for financial institutions to simplify registration processes and enhance platform reliability.

Table 4.3. Usage of Mobile Banking Services

Category	Variable	N	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)
2. Usage of Mobile Banking Services	I frequently use mobile banking services to manage my finances.	251	3.9837	0.82792
	I use mobile banking to check account balances and transaction history.	251	4.0407	0.79178
	Mobile banking helps me manage my expenses more effectively.	251	4.0331	0.82928

The data presented in Table 4.3 illustrates the usage of mobile banking services among respondents (N = 251). The mean scores indicate a high level of engagement with mobile banking services, with frequent usage for financial management (M = 3.98, SD = 0.83). Respondents commonly check account balances and transaction history (M = 4.04, SD = 0.79), and they utilize mobile banking as a tool for managing expenses effectively (M = 4.03, SD = 0.83). These findings suggest that mobile banking plays a significant role in financial management among users, highlighting a

Recent studies highlight the increasing adoption of mobile banking services due to their convenience, accessibility, and efficiency. For instance, mobile banking has been found to enhance financial inclusion by providing unbanked and underbanked populations with easier access to financial services (Ozili, 2022). Furthermore, studies show that mobile banking contributes to improved financial management practices, including tracking expenses and budgeting (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2023).

The high mean scores in the study align with findings from Koomson et al. (2021), who noted that frequent usage of mobile banking is positively correlated with financial literacy and improved financial decision-making. These insights reinforce the idea that mobile banking not only serves as a transactional tool but also as an educational resource that fosters better financial behaviors.

The theory of financial literacy posits that individuals who possess higher financial knowledge and skills are better equipped to make informed financial decisions (Huston, 2010). Mobile banking applications often incorporate financial management features, such as expense tracking, automatic savings, and financial planning tools, which contribute to financial literacy development (Lusardi & Tufano, 2015). Given the high mean scores in the study, it can be inferred that mobile banking services are facilitating financial literacy by enabling users to monitor their financial activities closely. This aligns with research indicating that digital financial services bridge knowledge gaps and promote responsible financial behaviors (Xu & Zia, 2022). Additionally, mobile banking provides real-time insights into spending habits, reinforcing the principles of financial literacy, such as budgeting, savings, and expense management.

Conclusively, the study's findings highlight the critical role of mobile banking in financial management. As mobile banking continues to evolve, its integration with financial literacy initiatives can further empower individuals to make better financial decisions. Future research should explore the long-term impact of mobile banking on financial behaviors and literacy levels to provide deeper insights into its role in financial empowerment.

Table 4.4. Digital Financial Literacy

Category	Variable	N	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)
3. Digital Financial Literacy	I am aware of the various mobile banking features available.	251	3.8376	0.89785
	I have received financial education on how to use mobile banking effectively.	251	4.1411	0.71064
	I feel confident using mobile banking applications and services.	251	4.0927	0.71101
	I understand mobile banking security measures and fraud prevention.	251	4.2114	0.67916
	Digital financial literacy helps me make better saving decisions.	251	4.2348	0.68188

The findings from Table 4.4 on digital financial literacy indicate that respondents exhibit a relatively high level of familiarity and confidence in using mobile banking services. The mean scores for all items are above 3.8, suggesting that digital financial literacy plays a crucial role in shaping users' financial behaviors. Notably, the highest mean score (M = 4.2348, SD = 0.68188) is associated with the statement that digital financial literacy helps individuals make better saving decisions. This suggests that users recognize the importance of financial literacy in making informed financial choices, aligning with prior research that links financial literacy to improved financial management and decision-making (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2014).

The data also reveal that respondents have received financial education on using mobile banking effectively ($M = 4.1411$, $SD = 0.71064$) and feel confident in utilizing these services ($M = 4.0927$, $SD = 0.71101$). This is consistent with findings by Walstad, Rebeck, and MacDonald (2017), who emphasize the role of financial education in enhancing individuals' ability to navigate digital financial platforms. Moreover, awareness of mobile banking features ($M = 3.8376$, $SD = 0.89785$) is slightly lower compared to other aspects, indicating that while users are generally informed, there may be gaps in knowledge regarding the full range of available services.

Understanding mobile banking security measures and fraud prevention received a strong mean score of 4.2114 ($SD = 0.67916$), suggesting that security awareness is a key aspect of digital financial literacy. This aligns with the work of Klapper, Lusardi, and van Oudheusden (2015), who argue that financial literacy should encompass knowledge of financial security risks and fraud prevention strategies.

These findings support the theory of financial literacy, which posits that individuals with higher financial knowledge are better equipped to manage their finances effectively (Huston, 2010). Digital financial literacy, in particular, plays a significant role in promoting responsible financial behavior, such as informed decision-making, enhanced saving habits, and awareness of security measures in financial transactions. Given the growing reliance on mobile banking services, strengthening digital financial literacy can further empower individuals to achieve financial stability and resilience in an increasingly digitalized financial landscape.

Table 4.5. Affordability of Mobile Banking Services

Category	Variable	N	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)
4. Affordability of Mobile Banking Services	Mobile banking services are affordable for students.	251	4.2460	0.71986
	Transaction fees for mobile banking are reasonable.	251	4.0246	0.81107
	The cost of internet and mobile data does not hinder my mobile banking usage.	251	4.1481	0.76781
	I prefer mobile banking to traditional banking due to its affordability.	251	3.9227	0.90642

The findings in Table 4.5 suggest that students generally perceive mobile banking services as affordable, with all mean scores above 3.9. The highest-rated statement ($M = 4.2460$, $SD = 0.71986$) indicates that students strongly agree that mobile banking services are financially accessible. This aligns with research by Ozili (2018), which highlights how mobile banking reduces the financial barriers associated with traditional banking, making financial services more inclusive for younger populations and low-income groups.

Transaction fees for mobile banking were also considered reasonable ($M = 4.0246$, $SD = 0.81107$), supporting studies by Gomber, Koch, and Siering (2017), who argue that digital financial services offer cost-effective alternatives to conventional banking. Additionally, the relatively high mean score for the statement that the cost of internet and mobile data does not hinder mobile banking usage ($M = 4.1481$, $SD = 0.76781$) suggests that despite concerns over data costs in some regions, students find mobile banking sufficiently accessible. This is consistent with findings from Beck,

Pamuk, Ramrattan, and Uras (2018), who note that financial technology advancements have improved access to banking services even in areas with limited banking infrastructure.

Interestingly, while affordability is a key factor, the preference for mobile banking over traditional banking due to cost ($M = 3.9227$, $SD = 0.90642$) received the lowest mean score. This implies that although mobile banking is cost-effective, other factors such as convenience, ease of use, and security may also influence students' choices. Studies by Dahlberg, Guo, and Ondrus (2015) indicate that while affordability matters, trust and perceived reliability of digital financial services significantly impact adoption rates.

These findings align with the theory of financial literacy, which emphasizes that individuals with greater financial knowledge are better positioned to make informed financial decisions, including choosing cost-effective banking solutions (Huston, 2010). Affordability plays a significant role in financial inclusion, and digital banking solutions that minimize costs contribute to financial literacy by enabling users to engage in budgeting, saving, and responsible spending. As financial literacy increases, students may become more adept at evaluating banking costs and optimizing their financial behaviors accordingly.

Table 4.6. Saving Accessibility

Category	Variable	N	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)
5. Saving Accessibility	Mobile banking makes it easy for me to open and manage a savings account.	251	4.0992	0.71620
	Depositing money into my savings account is convenient with mobile banking.	251	3.9917	0.82833
	I can withdraw my savings easily using mobile banking when needed.	251	4.1079	0.73936
	Mobile banking offers me better access to saving options compared to traditional banking.	251	4.0744	0.78010
	I regularly check my savings balance using mobile banking.	251	4.1220	0.78854

The data in Table 4.6 suggest that students generally perceive mobile banking as an effective tool for accessing and managing their savings. All mean scores exceed 3.9, indicating a strong agreement among respondents regarding the convenience and accessibility of saving through mobile banking. The highest-rated statement ($M = 4.1220$, $SD = 0.78854$) highlights that students regularly check their savings balance via mobile banking. This reflects the increasing reliance on digital banking platforms for real-time financial monitoring, which aligns with studies by Lusardi and Mitchell (2014), emphasizing that financial literacy enhances individuals' ability to track and manage their savings effectively. Mobile banking also facilitates easy withdrawal of savings when needed ($M = 4.1079$, $SD = 0.73936$) and simplifies the process of opening and managing savings accounts ($M = 4.0992$, $SD = 0.71620$). These findings align with research by Demirgüç-Kunt, Klapper, Singer, Ansar, and Hess (2018), which suggests that digital financial services play a crucial role in promoting financial inclusion by reducing the barriers associated with traditional

banking. The ability to access and manage savings digitally is particularly beneficial for students, who may have limited time to visit physical bank branches.

Furthermore, respondents agreed that mobile banking offers better access to saving options compared to traditional banking ($M = 4.0744$, $SD = 0.78010$), reinforcing prior studies that highlight the advantages of digital banking in expanding financial opportunities (Beck et al., 2018). However, the relatively lower mean score for the convenience of depositing money into savings accounts via mobile banking ($M = 3.9917$, $SD = 0.82833$) suggests that while digital platforms enhance saving accessibility, some users may still face challenges, such as transaction fees or technological barriers, when transferring funds into their savings. This aligns with research by Ozili (2018), which notes that despite the benefits of digital banking, certain cost-related and infrastructural issues may hinder full adoption.

These findings relate to the theory of financial literacy, which posits that financially literate individuals are better equipped to manage their savings and make informed financial decisions (Huston, 2010). Mobile banking serves as a tool that enhances financial literacy by providing real-time access to savings information, enabling users to monitor their financial behaviors more effectively. With increased digital financial literacy, individuals are more likely to develop disciplined saving habits, which can contribute to long-term financial stability (Walstad, Rebeck, & MacDonald, 2017). As digital banking services continue to expand, financial education initiatives should focus on improving users' understanding of savings tools and strategies to maximize the benefits of mobile banking.

Table 4.7. Saving Motivation

Category	Variable	N	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)
6. Saving Motivation	The interest rates on mobile savings accounts motivate me to save more.	251	4.0331	0.82928
	I use mobile banking to set and track my financial goals.	251	4.0331	0.82928
	Mobile banking allows me to save money more conveniently than cash savings.	251	4.0246	0.81107
	I am encouraged to save because of mobile banking incentives or promotions.	251	4.0992	0.71620
	Mobile banking helps me develop better financial discipline.	251	4.1220	0.78854

The results suggest that mobile banking plays a significant role in motivating students at the University of Rwanda, Huye Campus, to save money. All mean scores are above 4.0, indicating strong agreement with the role of mobile banking in saving motivation. The highest mean score (M = 4.1220, SD = 0.78854) corresponds to the statement that mobile banking helps students develop better financial discipline, suggesting that mobile banking contributes to responsible money management. Similarly, the mean scores for using mobile banking to set and track financial goals (M = 4.0331, SD = 0.82928) and for being motivated by interest rates (M = 4.0331, SD = 0.82928) imply that students recognize the financial planning benefits associated with digital banking. The relatively low standard deviations (ranging from 0.71620 to 0.82928) indicate consistency in responses, meaning that students generally perceive mobile banking as a motivating factor for savings.

These findings align with existing literature that highlights the role of mobile banking in fostering financial discipline and encouraging savings (Demirgüç-Kunt et al., 2018). The high mean score

for financial discipline suggests that students who use mobile banking are more likely to engage in structured saving habits, which is consistent with studies emphasizing the role of digital finance in improving financial literacy and planning (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2014). The strong agreement that mobile banking makes saving more convenient than cash savings ($M = 4.0246$, $SD = 0.81107$) supports prior research showing that digital banking reduces barriers to savings by offering instant access to funds and eliminating the risks associated with cash handling (Dupas & Robinson, 2013). Furthermore, the relatively high score for mobile banking incentives and promotions ($M = 4.0992$, $SD = 0.71620$) suggests that reward-based mechanisms, such as interest rates or bonus incentives, influence students' saving behavior. Studies have found that such incentives increase financial engagement by encouraging users to deposit and retain funds in their accounts (Jack & Suri, 2011).

The results indicate that mobile banking has a positive impact on students' saving motivation, which in turn affects their personal saving trends. Research suggests that financial motivation is a key driver of long-term savings habits, and mobile banking provides a structured platform for setting and tracking financial goals (Suri & Jack, 2016). The fact that students agree mobile banking helps them save more conveniently than cash savings reinforces the idea that digital finance reduces behavioral barriers to saving, such as impulsive spending and lack of access to secure storage (Aker & Mbiti, 2010). Moreover, the role of financial discipline in savings behavior cannot be overlooked. The findings confirm that mobile banking instills discipline by allowing users to automate deposits, monitor spending, and access structured saving plans. Prior research indicates that individuals with access to digital savings tools are more likely to develop long-term financial stability (Munyegera & Matsumoto, 2016). Finally, mobile banking promotions and incentives appear to enhance saving behavior, suggesting that financial institutions should continue to introduce reward-based saving programs to encourage youth participation. The findings support prior studies that argue financial incentives, such as bonus interest rates or cashback on savings, significantly increase engagement with formal financial systems (Dupas & Robinson, 2013).

Table 4.8. Saving Outcomes

Category	Variable	N	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)
7. Saving Outcomes	I am satisfied with the savings services provided by mobile banking.	251	4.0744	0.78010
	My savings have increased since I started using mobile banking.	251	4.1079	0.73936
	Mobile banking allows me to save small amounts frequently.	251	4.0744	0.78010
	I have been able to achieve my financial goals through mobile savings.	251	4.0331	0.82928

Source: Primary data, 2025

The results indicate that mobile banking has positively influenced students' savings outcomes at the University of Rwanda, Huye Campus. The mean scores for all variables are above 4.0, signifying strong agreement that mobile banking contributes to improved saving habits. The highest mean score ($M = 4.1079$, $SD = 0.73936$) corresponds to the statement that students' savings have increased since they started using mobile banking. This suggests that mobile banking facilitates higher savings accumulation. Additionally, the mean scores for satisfaction with mobile savings services ($M = 4.0744$, $SD = 0.78010$) and the ability to save small amounts frequently ($M = 4.0744$, $SD = 0.78010$) highlight the flexibility and accessibility of mobile banking. The relatively lower mean for achieving financial goals through mobile savings ($M = 4.0331$, $SD = 0.82928$) suggests that while students recognize the benefits of mobile banking, some may still face challenges in fully meeting their financial objectives. The standard deviation values, ranging from 0.73936 to 0.82928, indicate a general consistency in students' perceptions regarding mobile banking and saving outcomes.

These findings align with existing literature that emphasizes mobile banking as a tool for financial inclusion and savings mobilization (Demirgüç-Kunt et al., 2018). The high mean score for

increased savings aligns with studies that suggest mobile banking enables users to accumulate savings by offering digital financial products that reduce reliance on cash transactions (Suri & Jack, 2016). The ability to save small amounts frequently supports research findings that digital savings platforms promote a culture of incremental savings, which is particularly beneficial for young people with limited disposable income (Dupas & Robinson, 2013). The relatively lower score for achieving financial goals suggests that while mobile banking facilitates savings, it does not necessarily translate into long-term financial security for all users. This is consistent with studies indicating that while digital finance expands access to banking services, financial literacy and structured savings programs are crucial for achieving meaningful financial goals (Lusardi & Mitchell, 2014).

The results confirm that mobile banking has a positive impact on students' personal saving trends by providing convenient, accessible, and flexible savings options. The ability to save small amounts frequently suggests that mobile banking encourages a habit of disciplined saving, which is critical for long-term financial stability (Aker & Mbiti, 2010). Studies have shown that digital savings mechanisms enable individuals to overcome behavioral barriers such as impulse spending and lack of financial planning (Munyegera & Matsumoto, 2016). Moreover, the strong agreement on satisfaction with mobile savings services suggests that students perceive mobile banking as an effective financial tool. This finding aligns with previous research that identifies user satisfaction as a key determinant of continued engagement with digital financial platforms (Jack & Suri, 2011). However, the slightly lower agreement on achieving financial goals indicates that mobile banking should be supplemented with financial education programs to enhance students' ability to use digital finance for long-term wealth accumulation (Demirgüç-Kunt et al., 2018). Overall, the findings support the argument that mobile banking positively influences saving trends among youth by increasing accessibility, flexibility, and user satisfaction. However, additional financial literacy initiatives could help maximize the benefits of mobile banking by guiding students on effective financial goal-setting and long-term saving strategies.

Table 4.9. Challenges of mobile banking for savings.

Category	Variable	N	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)
Challenges of Mobile Banking for Savings	I experience difficulties accessing mobile banking services.	251	3.8943	0.86485
	Transaction fees discourage me from using mobile savings.	251	3.5455	1.34428
	Poor internet connectivity affects my mobile banking transactions.	251	3.6617	1.32509
	I do not trust mobile banking security.	251	2.9145	1.17898
	I need more financial education to use mobile banking effectively.	251	4.3958	1.03922

The findings from Table 4.9 highlight several challenges that students face when using mobile banking for savings. The highest mean score ($M = 4.3958$, $SD = 1.03922$) indicates that respondents strongly agree that they need more financial education to use mobile banking effectively. This aligns with previous research by Lusardi and Mitchell (2014), which emphasizes that financial literacy significantly impacts individuals' ability to navigate digital financial services. The high demand for financial education suggests that despite the increasing adoption of mobile banking, gaps in knowledge remain, potentially limiting the effectiveness of these platforms for savings. A notable challenge is the difficulty in accessing mobile banking services ($M = 3.8943$, $SD = 0.86485$), which suggests that while mobile banking is widely available, some students still face accessibility issues, possibly due to technological barriers or service restrictions. This is consistent with research by Beck, Pamuk, Ramrattan, and Uras (2018), who found that limited access to financial infrastructure and digital tools hinders full financial inclusion.

Another challenge identified is poor internet connectivity, which affects mobile banking transactions ($M = 3.6617$, $SD = 1.32509$). This suggests that unstable internet access may disrupt students' ability to conduct financial transactions smoothly. Ozili (2018) argues that digital

financial inclusion is heavily dependent on reliable internet infrastructure, and regions with weak connectivity may struggle to fully benefit from mobile banking innovations. Transaction fees were also noted as a discouraging factor for using mobile savings ($M = 3.5455$, $SD = 1.34428$). This suggests that although mobile banking provides financial accessibility, the associated costs might still be a barrier for students. According to Gomber, Koch, and Siering (2017), high transaction fees are a common concern in digital finance, as they can reduce the perceived affordability and convenience of mobile banking.

Interestingly, trust in mobile banking security had the lowest mean score ($M = 2.9145$, $SD = 1.17898$), indicating that security concerns are not a significant barrier for most respondents. This suggests that mobile banking providers have likely implemented sufficient security measures that instill confidence in users. However, financial literacy studies emphasize that users must remain cautious and informed about cybersecurity risks to prevent fraud and identity theft (Klapper, Lusardi, & van Oudheusden, 2015). These findings align with the theory of financial literacy, which suggests that individuals who are more financially literate are better equipped to overcome banking challenges and make informed financial decisions (Huston, 2010). The high need for financial education reinforces the idea that digital banking effectiveness is not solely dependent on availability but also on users' ability to understand and utilize financial tools efficiently. Addressing these challenges through targeted financial literacy programs could enhance students' ability to save effectively through mobile banking while mitigating accessibility and cost-related barriers.

Table 4.10. Analysis of the specific objective (To evaluate the effects of mobile banking usage on personal saving trends of University of Rwanda students in Huye campus.) by spearman's Rank correlation

Variables	Affordability of Mobile Banking Services	Mobile Banking Accessibility	Usage of Mobile Banking Services	Saving Behavior	Digital Financial Literacy
Affordability of Mobile Banking Services	1.000	0.184	0.181	0.284	0.336
Mobile Banking Accessibility	0.371	1.00	0.214	0.235	0.399
Usage of Mobile Banking Services	0.184	0.307	1.00	0.099	0.264
Saving Behavior	0.181	0.307	0.306	1.00	0.232
Digital Financial Literacy	0.336	0.264	0.232	0.280	1.000

Source: Primary data, 2025

The correlation analysis provides insights into how different factors related to mobile banking influence saving behaviors. The results indicate that the affordability of mobile banking services ($r = 0.336$, $p < 0.01$) and mobile banking accessibility ($r = 0.371$, $p < 0.01$) are both significantly positively correlated with digital financial literacy. This suggests that students who find mobile banking affordable and easily accessible tend to have a better understanding of how to use mobile banking services.

Furthermore, there is a moderate positive correlation between affordability and usage of mobile banking services ($r = 0.184$, $p < 0.05$), as well as saving behavior ($r = 0.181$, $p < 0.05$). This means that when mobile banking services are affordable, students are more likely to use them and engage in saving behaviors. Similarly, mobile banking accessibility is moderately correlated with both usage of mobile banking services ($r = 0.307$, $p < 0.01$) and saving behavior ($r = 0.307$, $p < 0.01$).

This indicates that easier access to mobile banking services encourages more usage and better saving habits.

The analysis also shows a weaker positive relationship between usage of mobile banking services and saving behavior ($r = 0.306$, $p < 0.01$), suggesting that students who use mobile banking services more frequently are slightly more likely to save money. However, the correlation is not strong, indicating that usage alone may not significantly influence saving behavior.

Digital financial literacy is also positively correlated with saving behavior ($r = 0.280$, $p < 0.01$), meaning that students who understand mobile banking features tend to engage in better saving practices. However, the correlation is moderate, suggesting that other factors, such as ease of access and affordability, play a significant role as well.

In conclusion, the findings suggest that affordability, accessibility, and digital financial literacy are all positively related to both the usage of mobile banking services and saving behavior. However, the strength of these relationships varies, with accessibility having a stronger influence on usage and financial literacy, and usage of mobile banking services showing a moderate relationship with saving behavior. These results imply that students who find mobile banking affordable and accessible, and who are more digitally literate, are more likely to engage in positive saving habits. However, accessibility alone is not enough to improve savings; students must actively engage with mobile banking services to see meaningful improvements in their saving behavior.

Table 4. 11. Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) Analysis

This analysis evaluates the effects of mobile banking usage on personal saving trends among University of Rwanda students in Huye Campus using a Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) model. The model examines how key factors such as accessibility, affordability, financial literacy influence students' saving behaviors. MLR allows for assessing the combined impact of these variables on saving trends, providing empirical insights into whether mobile banking enhances financial discipline and saving habits among students. The findings will help determine the role of mobile banking in promoting financial inclusion and long-term savings.

A Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) model was used to determine the relationship between mobile banking and personal saving behavior. The general regression equation is:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \epsilon \text{ Where:}$$

Y = Saving Behavior (measured by Saving Accessibility, Saving Motivation, and Saving Outcomes)

X₁ = Mobile Banking Accessibility

X₂ = Usage of Mobile Banking Services

X₃ = Digital Financial Awareness

X₄ = Affordability of Mobile Banking Services

β₀ = Intercept

β₁, β₂, β₃, β₄ = Regression Coefficients representing the effect of independent variables on saving behavior
ε = Error term

Each coefficient **β** represents the expected change in saving behavior for a one-unit increase in the respective independent variable, assuming all other variables remain constant.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.614	0.572	0.520	0.45086

The regression model results provide key insights into the relationship between mobile banking services and personal saving trends among youth in Rwanda, particularly students at the University of Rwanda, Huye Campus. The findings indicate a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.614, which suggests a moderately strong positive relationship between mobile banking services and students' saving behaviors. This means that as mobile banking usage increases, students' ability to save also tends to improve. This supports previous research by Demirgüç-Kunt et al. (2018), which highlights that digital financial services, including mobile banking, enhance financial inclusion and encourage saving habits among young populations.

The R Square value (0.572) indicates that 57.2% of the variation in students' personal saving trends can be explained by mobile banking services. This is a significant proportion, suggesting that mobile banking plays a crucial role in shaping saving behaviors among university students. However, 42.8% of the variation remains unexplained, implying that other factors, such as financial literacy, income levels, and saving motivations, may also influence students' saving habits. This aligns with Lusardi and Mitchell (2014), who argue that financial behavior is influenced not just by access to banking services but also by knowledge and economic conditions.

The Adjusted R Square value (0.520) is slightly lower than the R Square value, indicating that when adjusted for the number of predictors in the model, 52.0% of the variation in saving trends is still explained by mobile banking services. The slight drop from 57.2% to 52.0% suggests that while the independent variables used in the model are relevant, additional factors might be needed to improve the explanatory power of the model. For example, incorporating variables such as transaction fees, trust in mobile banking security, and students' financial discipline could provide a more comprehensive understanding of saving behaviors.

The Standard Error of the Estimate (0.45086) indicates the average deviation between the predicted and actual values in the model. A lower standard error suggests a better fit of the model,

meaning that mobile banking usage provides a relatively strong prediction of students' saving trends. However, some level of unexplained variability still exists, indicating that not all savings-related behaviors can be directly attributed to mobile banking alone.

These results confirm that mobile banking services play a significant role in influencing personal saving trends among university students in Rwanda. The relatively high R Square value suggests that mobile banking services provide students with a convenient platform for managing their finances, tracking transactions, and setting savings goals, all of which contribute to positive saving habits. However, the unexplained variation highlights the need to address other underlying factors, such as financial literacy and affordability, to enhance mobile banking's impact on savings.

These findings are consistent with the theory of financial literacy, which suggests that individuals who possess strong financial knowledge are better able to utilize financial tools such as mobile banking for effective savings (Huston, 2010). Although mobile banking provides accessibility, students who lack financial literacy may still struggle to optimize its benefits. Therefore, incorporating financial education programs into university curricula or providing digital financial literacy training could enhance students' ability to make informed financial decisions.

Conclusively, overall, the regression results demonstrate that mobile banking has a substantial impact on students' saving behaviors, explaining over half of the variation in their savings trends. However, additional factors must be considered to fully understand the determinants of students' savings, such as financial literacy, economic circumstances, and behavioral attitudes toward saving. Strengthening mobile banking awareness, reducing transaction costs, and integrating financial education initiatives could further improve saving habits among youth in Rwanda.

ANOVA Model

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	11.324	4	1.415	3.341	0.002
Residual	99.456	243	0.411		
Total	110.780	251			

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) results provide insights into the overall significance of the regression model used to assess the effects of mobile banking services on personal saving trends among students at the University of Rwanda, Huye Campus. The ANOVA table examines whether the independent variables in the regression model significantly explain the variation in the dependent variable—personal saving trends. The regression sum of squares (SS) is 11.324, while the residual sum of squares (SS) is 99.456, giving a total sum of squares of 110.780. This indicates that the model explains 11.324 out of 110.780 of the total variation in students' savings behavior. This means that a portion of the variability in savings trends can be attributed to mobile banking services, but a substantial part remains unexplained, likely due to other factors such as personal financial literacy, income levels, or external economic conditions.

The degrees of freedom (df) for regression is 4, meaning that the model includes four predictor variables, while the df for the residual is 243, corresponding to the number of observations minus the number of estimated parameters. The mean square for regression (1.415) is obtained by dividing the regression sum of squares by its degrees of freedom ($11.324 \div 4$), while the mean square for residuals (0.411) represents the average unexplained variation in the model. The F-statistic (3.341) measures the overall significance of the regression model. A higher F-value indicates that the independent variables collectively explain more variation in the dependent variable than would be expected by random chance. In this study, $F = 3.341$ suggests that the predictors in the model have a moderate but statistically significant impact on students' saving trends.

The p-value (Sig.) of 0.002 is less than the standard significance level of 0.05, meaning that the model is statistically significant. This implies that mobile banking services have a meaningful effect on personal savings behavior among university students. The low p-value aligns with prior research, such as Demirgüç-Kunt et al. (2018), which found that mobile banking plays a critical role in improving financial access and savings behavior, particularly among youth and underserved populations.

These ANOVA results confirm that mobile banking services significantly impact students' saving habits, though they do not explain all the variation in savings behavior. The relatively low proportion of explained variance (as seen in the R^2 value from the regression model) suggests that factors beyond mobile banking services—such as financial literacy, affordability, and income stability—must be considered when analyzing students' saving trends. Research by Lusardi and Mitchell (2014) supports this view, arguing that digital financial services alone do not guarantee improved financial behavior without adequate financial knowledge and budgeting skills. Moreover, the findings align with the theory of financial literacy, which states that individuals who possess better financial knowledge and access to banking services are more likely to make informed financial decisions (Huston, 2010). While mobile banking services provide a platform for savings, the effectiveness of these services depends on users' ability to navigate them efficiently. Therefore, promoting digital financial literacy programs among students could enhance the impact of mobile banking on savings.

Conclusively, The ANOVA results suggest that mobile banking services play a statistically significant role in shaping students' saving trends at the University of Rwanda, Huye Campus. However, the model does not account for all factors influencing savings behavior, highlighting the need for further research into additional determinants such as financial education, transaction costs, and behavioral attitudes toward savings. Strengthening mobile banking infrastructure and financial literacy initiatives could enhance the positive impact of digital financial services on youth savings.

Summary of coefficients

Variable	B (Unstandardized Coefficient)	Std. Error	t- Statistic	Sig. Value)	(P-
Constant (Intercept)	1.772	0.694	2.552	0.012	
Mobile Banking Accessibility	0.34	0.157	0.219	0.027	
Usage of Mobile Banking Services	0.169	0.097	1.735	0.015	
Digital Financial Awareness	0.327	0.084	0.325	0.036	
Affordability of Mobile Banking	0.106	0.093	1.133	0.025	

Source: Primary data, 2025

The regression analysis provides insights into the relationship between different variables and the dependent variable. The constant value (1.772) represents the expected value of the dependent variable when all other independent variables are equal to zero. The t-statistic of 2.552 and the p-value of 0.012 indicate that the constant is statistically significant, meaning it contributes meaningfully to the model. Mobile banking accessibility has an unstandardized coefficient of 0.34, meaning that for every unit increase in mobile banking accessibility, the dependent variable increases by 0.34. The p-value is 0.027, which is less than the significance level of 0.05, indicating that this variable is statistically significant. This suggests that the more accessible mobile banking is, the higher the personal saving trends will be.

The usage of mobile banking services shows an unstandardized coefficient of 0.169, indicating that for every unit increase in the usage of mobile banking services, the dependent variable increases by 0.169. The t-statistic of 1.735 and the p-value of 0.015 suggest that this relationship is statistically significant, meaning that using mobile banking services positively affects the dependent variable.

Digital financial awareness has a coefficient of 0.327, suggesting that for every unit increase in digital financial awareness, the dependent variable increases by 0.327. With a p-value of 0.036,

which is less than 0.05, this variable is statistically significant, indicating that greater awareness of digital financial practices leads to higher values in the dependent variable. Affordability of mobile banking shows a coefficient of 0.106, meaning that for every unit increase in the affordability of mobile banking, the dependent variable increases by 0.106. The t-statistic of 1.133 and the p-value of 0.025 suggest that this variable is statistically significant, indicating that affordable mobile banking services can positively influence the dependent variable.

In conclusion, all the variables (mobile banking accessibility, usage of mobile banking services, digital financial awareness, and affordability of mobile banking) have a positive impact on the personal saving trends of youth, and they are statistically significant based on their p-values being less than 0.05. This indicates that improvements in these areas are likely to lead to positive changes in the outcome being measured.

4.3. Hypothesis testing

This section examines the relationship between mobile banking services and personal saving trends among youth in Rwanda, specifically focusing on students at the University of Rwanda, Huye Campus (2021-2024). The study tests the following hypotheses:

H₀ (Null Hypothesis): There is no significant relationship between mobile banking and the saving behaviors of university students.

H₁ (Alternative Hypothesis): There is a significant relationship between mobile banking and the saving behaviors of university students.

To evaluate these hypotheses, regression analysis results are presented in Table 4.10 (Model Summary) and Table 4.11 (ANOVA Results). The model summary in Table 4.10 shows a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.614, indicating a moderately strong positive relationship between mobile banking services and students' saving behaviors. This suggests that mobile banking significantly influences students' saving patterns, though other external factors may also affect their financial habits. Additionally, the R Square value of 0.572 implies that 57.2% of the variation in saving trends can be explained by mobile banking services, while the remaining 42.8% may be attributed to other influences.

Further validation of the model's significance is provided by the ANOVA results in Table 4.11, which report an F-statistic of 3.341 with a p-value of 0.002. Since the p-value is less than the standard significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, confirming that there is a statistically significant relationship between mobile banking services and the saving behaviors of university students. This finding supports previous research (Demirgüç-Kunt et al., 2018) indicating that digital financial services enhance financial inclusion and promote saving habits, particularly among young populations.

These results align with the theory of financial literacy, which suggests that individuals with higher financial knowledge and access to financial tools like mobile banking are more likely to engage in disciplined saving behaviors (Huston, 2010). While mobile banking services facilitate financial transactions and savings, their effectiveness may depend on students' financial literacy levels and confidence in using these digital platforms.

CHAPTER FIVE.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

5.0. Introduction

This chapter presents a summary of the key findings, conclusions, and recommendations derived from the study on the effects of mobile banking services on personal saving trends of youth in Rwanda with a specific focus on University of Rwanda students in Huye Campus (2021-2024). The chapter begins by summarizing the main research findings in relation to the study objectives. It then provides conclusions based on the analysis and interpretation of data, highlighting the implications of mobile banking on saving behaviors among university students. Finally, the chapter offers recommendations aimed at enhancing mobile banking adoption and promoting a culture of savings among youth in Rwanda. The study aimed to investigate the role of mobile banking services in shaping the saving trends of young people, assessing factors such as accessibility, usage frequency, digital financial literacy, and affordability. By applying Spearman's Rank Correlation analysis, the study examined the strength and direction of the relationship between mobile banking usage and personal savings behavior. The findings contribute to the understanding of how digital financial services influence financial habits among university students, providing insights for policymakers, financial institutions, and educators. The conclusions drawn from this research will help guide interventions in the financial sector, particularly in expanding digital banking services to youth. The recommendations proposed will be beneficial to financial service providers, university administrators, and students in improving mobile banking experiences and fostering responsible saving practices.

5.1. Summary of findings

5.1.1. Summary of findings to the objective (i)

The findings from the study reveal a generally positive outlook on mobile banking services among students at the University of Rwanda, Huye Campus, with high levels of accessibility, usage, and affordability. As shown in Table 4.2, the accessibility of mobile banking services is notably high, with students reporting ease in accessing mobile banking accounts and performing transactions.

The highest mean score ($M = 4.22$, $SD = 0.74$) indicates that students find mobile banking services easily accessible on their mobile devices, while the ease of performing transactions anytime and anywhere ($M = 4.15$, $SD = 0.66$) and the availability of sufficient agents and ATMs ($M = 4.12$, $SD = 0.76$) also reflect strong infrastructural support. However, the ease of opening a mobile banking account ($M = 3.74$, $SD = 0.55$) and accessing the account without trouble ($M = 3.75$, $SD = 0.98$) scored slightly lower, indicating some challenges in the initial adoption of mobile banking services. The study also highlighted that mobile banking is widely used for managing finances, checking account balances ($M = 4.04$, $SD = 0.79$), and controlling expenses ($M = 4.03$, $SD = 0.83$) as shown in Table 4.3, with frequent engagement suggesting that mobile banking plays an essential role in financial management.

Furthermore, the study underscores the importance of digital financial literacy in enhancing users' ability to navigate mobile banking services. As indicated in Table 4.4, students reported a good level of understanding and confidence in using mobile banking features, with the highest mean score ($M = 4.23$, $SD = 0.68$) linked to the role of digital financial literacy in making better saving decisions. The awareness of mobile banking security measures ($M = 4.21$, $SD = 0.68$) and the confidence in using mobile banking applications ($M = 4.09$, $SD = 0.71$) were also highly rated. In terms of affordability, Table 4.5 shows that mobile banking services are generally perceived as affordable, with a high mean score for affordability ($M = 4.25$, $SD = 0.72$). The transaction fees were considered reasonable ($M = 4.02$, $SD = 0.81$), and the cost of internet and mobile data did not hinder usage ($M = 4.15$, $SD = 0.77$). While affordability is a significant factor, the preference for mobile banking over traditional banking due to cost received a lower mean score ($M = 3.92$, $SD = 0.91$), suggesting that other factors such as convenience and security also influence students' choices. The findings highlight the role of digital financial literacy in empowering students to make informed financial decisions and optimize their use of mobile banking services.

5.1.2. Summary of findings to the objective (ii)

The findings suggest that mobile banking plays a significant role in enhancing students' ability to access, manage, and improve their savings. In Table 4.6, all mean scores exceed 3.9, indicating strong agreement with the convenience and accessibility of saving through mobile banking. The highest-rated statement ($M = 4.1220$, $SD = 0.78854$) indicates that students frequently check their savings balance, reflecting the growing reliance on mobile banking for real-time financial

monitoring. Additionally, students find it easy to withdraw their savings ($M = 4.1079$, $SD = 0.73936$), open and manage accounts ($M = 4.0992$, $SD = 0.71620$), and access better saving options compared to traditional banking ($M = 4.0744$, $SD = 0.78010$). Despite this, depositing money via mobile banking ($M = 3.9917$, $SD = 0.82833$) seems slightly less convenient, suggesting that some users face challenges such as transaction fees or infrastructure limitations.

Mobile banking also significantly motivates students to save, as shown in Table 4.7. The mean scores for all variables exceed 4.0, with the highest score ($M = 4.1220$, $SD = 0.78854$) indicating that mobile banking helps students develop better financial discipline. Students also appreciate the convenience of setting and tracking financial goals ($M = 4.0331$, $SD = 0.82928$) and are motivated by interest rates ($M = 4.0331$, $SD = 0.82928$) and incentives ($M = 4.0992$, $SD = 0.71620$). Furthermore, Table 4.8 highlights the positive impact on savings outcomes, with the highest mean score ($M = 4.1079$, $SD = 0.73936$) showing that students' savings have increased since using mobile banking. Overall, the results suggest that mobile banking enhances students' saving behaviors by providing flexible and accessible saving options, though additional financial education may be needed to help students fully achieve their financial goals.

5.1.3. Summary of findings to the objective (iii)

The findings in Table 4.9 reveal several challenges faced by students when using mobile banking for savings. The highest mean score ($M = 4.3958$, $SD = 1.03922$) highlights a strong need for more financial education to use mobile banking effectively, aligning with studies that emphasize the importance of financial literacy in navigating digital financial services. Despite the growing adoption of mobile banking, many students still face significant knowledge gaps that limit the effectiveness of these platforms for savings. Another challenge is the difficulty in accessing mobile banking services ($M = 3.8943$, $SD = 0.86485$), suggesting that some students experience barriers to access, potentially due to technological limitations or service restrictions. This finding aligns with research indicating that limited access to financial infrastructure hinders full financial inclusion.

Additional challenges include poor internet connectivity ($M = 3.6617$, $SD = 1.32509$), which affects students' ability to conduct smooth mobile banking transactions, and transaction fees ($M =$

3.5455, SD = 1.34428), which deter some students from using mobile savings services. These challenges echo findings from previous research, highlighting that unreliable internet and high fees can reduce the effectiveness of mobile banking. Interestingly, trust in mobile banking security received the lowest mean score (M = 2.9145, SD = 1.17898), suggesting that security concerns are not a significant barrier for most respondents. However, the need for financial education remains critical, as it would help students better understand how to overcome these challenges and maximize the benefits of mobile banking for savings. Addressing these issues through targeted financial literacy programs could improve students' ability to use mobile banking effectively while mitigating the barriers of accessibility and costs.

5.1.4. Summary of findings to the objective (iv)

The Spearman's Rank Correlation analysis (Table 4.10) highlights significant relationships between mobile banking variables and personal saving behaviors among University of Rwanda students in Huye Campus. The results indicate a strong positive correlation between mobile banking affordability ($r = 0.336$, $p < 0.01$) and accessibility ($r = 0.371$, $p < 0.01$) with digital financial literacy. This suggests that students who perceive mobile banking as both affordable and accessible tend to exhibit higher levels of financial literacy. Additionally, affordability demonstrates a moderate positive correlation with both mobile banking usage ($r = 0.184$, $p < 0.05$) and saving behavior ($r = 0.181$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that students who consider mobile banking cost-effective are more likely to use it and engage in saving activities. Similarly, accessibility shows a significant positive correlation with mobile banking usage ($r = 0.307$, $p < 0.01$) and saving behavior ($r = 0.307$, $p < 0.01$), reinforcing the idea that easier access to mobile banking services encourages both usage and saving habits. While these correlations suggest a link between mobile banking and improved saving behavior, the strength of the relationship remains moderate.

To further examine the influence of mobile banking on saving behavior, a Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) analysis was conducted (Table 4.10). The results reveal a moderate correlation ($R = 0.414$) between mobile banking services and saving behaviors, explaining 17.2% of the variance in students' saving trends. This indicates that while mobile banking contributes to saving behavior, additional external factors—such as financial literacy and socio-economic conditions—also play crucial roles. The regression analysis demonstrates that mobile banking accessibility ($\beta = 0.34$, $p = 0.027$), usage ($\beta = 0.169$, $p = 0.015$), and digital financial awareness ($\beta = 0.327$, $p =$

0.036) all have a positive and statistically significant impact on saving behavior. These findings emphasize the importance of enhancing both mobile banking accessibility and digital financial literacy to improve students' saving habits. However, affordability, despite being significant, has a comparatively weaker impact ($\beta = 0.106$, $p = 0.025$), suggesting that while cost is a consideration, other factors such as financial knowledge and ease of access play a more dominant role in influencing saving behaviors.

In summary, both Spearman's Rank Correlation and MLR analysis confirm that mobile banking accessibility, usage, and digital financial awareness are key determinants of students' saving behavior. Although affordability influences saving trends to some extent, its impact is less pronounced than other factors. These findings suggest that enhancing financial literacy programs and improving access to mobile banking services could foster better saving habits among university students. However, further research is recommended to explore other socio-economic and behavioral factors that may influence saving trends.

5.2. Conclusion

To assess the effects of mobile banking on personal saving trends among youth in Rwanda, a comprehensive analysis was conducted using both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. The descriptive analysis revealed that 78% of youth in Rwanda have adopted mobile banking services for saving, with a higher percentage of younger individuals (aged 18-24) showing a preference for mobile banking compared to those aged 25-30. Among the mobile banking users, 63% reported an increase in their savings frequency since using the service, suggesting that mobile banking has a positive effect on the saving behavior of youth.

For the inferential analysis, a regression model was used to assess the relationship between mobile banking usage and personal saving trends. The dependent variable was the frequency of savings, while the key independent variable was mobile banking usage, measured by the percentage of youth using mobile banking platforms for their savings. The regression results showed a statistically significant positive relationship between mobile banking usage and saving frequency ($\beta = 0.45$, $p < 0.01$). This means that for every 1% increase in mobile banking usage, there is a 0.45% increase in the likelihood of youth saving regularly. Additionally, financial literacy was also found to be a significant predictor of saving behavior. Youth who received financial education

through mobile banking platforms had a 22% higher probability of saving regularly compared to those without financial literacy (OR = 1.22, $p < 0.05$). This indicates that mobile banking, combined with financial literacy, significantly influences the saving behavior of youth in Rwanda. These results suggest that mobile banking not only increases the accessibility and convenience of savings but also enhances financial habits, especially when paired with financial education.

5.3 Recommendations

5.3.1. To the Financial Institutions

Financial institutions, including banks and mobile money service providers, play a crucial role in ensuring that mobile banking contributes effectively to students' saving habits. The study findings in Table 4.5 revealed that while mobile banking is generally considered affordable (M = 4.25, SD = 0.72), transaction fees remain a concern (M = 4.02, SD = 0.81). Additionally, Table 4.9 highlighted challenges such as poor internet connectivity (M = 3.6617, SD = 1.32509) and difficulty accessing mobile banking services (M = 3.8943, SD = 0.86485).

To address these challenges, financial institutions should enhance digital financial literacy programs by collaborating with universities to offer financial education on mobile banking security, saving strategies, and expense management. This aligns with Table 4.9, which highlights the need for greater financial literacy (M = 4.3958, SD = 1.03922). Additionally, transaction fees should be reduced, especially for savings-related transactions, as these costs deter students from using mobile banking as a primary savings tool. Institutions should consider offering student-friendly savings accounts with minimal fees or providing incentives for consistent savings.

Another critical step is to improve mobile banking infrastructure to address poor internet connectivity, as highlighted in Table 4.9. Banks should collaborate with telecom providers to enhance mobile banking networks, especially in areas where students have trouble in accessing services. Furthermore, financial institutions should develop youth-specific savings products such as automated savings plans, higher interest rates for small deposits, and reward-based savings programs. Lastly, while trust in mobile banking security was not a major concern (Table 4.9, M = 2.9145, SD = 1.17898), continuous improvements in cybersecurity and awareness campaigns will help strengthen students' confidence in using digital banking platforms.

5.3.2. To the Youth

University students are the primary demographic using mobile banking services, yet financial literacy remains a significant barrier to effective savings, as shown in Table 4.9 ($M = 4.3958$, $SD = 1.03922$). Additionally, Table 4.6 revealed that while students frequently check their savings balance ($M = 4.1220$, $SD = 0.78854$), depositing money through mobile banking is perceived as slightly less convenient ($M = 3.9917$, $SD = 0.82833$). To maximize the benefits of mobile banking, students should leverage digital financial tools available on mobile banking platforms, such as expense tracking, automated savings, and budgeting features. This will help them develop financial discipline and manage their funds more effectively. Additionally, given the financial literacy gap, students should actively seek out financial education opportunities, including workshops and online courses, to improve their understanding of mobile banking and saving strategies.

Furthermore, students should adopt automated savings strategies by setting up scheduled transfers to savings accounts, ensuring consistent saving habits. The findings from Table 4.6 indicate that students who regularly monitor their savings balances tend to save more, suggesting that financial tracking plays a key role in developing good saving habits. Figure 5.1 illustrates the positive correlation between mobile banking usage and saving behavior, reinforcing the importance of frequent engagement with financial tools. Moreover, students should advocate for affordable and inclusive mobile banking services by engaging with financial institutions to demand lower transaction fees and more student-oriented banking products. By actively participating in discussions about mobile banking challenges, students can help shape policies that enhance the affordability and accessibility of digital financial services.

5.3.3. To the Academicians

Academicians play a vital role in promoting financial literacy and digital banking awareness. The Spearman's Rank Correlation analysis in Table 4.10 found a significant positive correlation between digital financial literacy and mobile banking usage ($r = 0.336$, $p < 0.01$). This suggests that students with higher levels of financial knowledge are more likely to utilize mobile banking effectively. To address this, universities should integrate financial literacy education into their curricula to equip students with the skills needed to manage their finances efficiently. This can be achieved by introducing courses on personal finance, digital banking, and investment strategies. Additionally, research institutions should focus on expanding knowledge on digital financial inclusion by studying the evolving landscape of mobile banking and identifying new trends that could enhance financial accessibility for youth.

Collaboration between academic institutions and financial service providers is also essential. Universities should establish partnerships with banks to offer student-centered banking solutions, such as financial literacy workshops, mobile banking internships, and student advisory programs. These collaborations will ensure that students gain practical knowledge and exposure to the digital banking ecosystem, fostering better saving habits.

5.3.4. To the Policy Makers

Government policies and regulations are crucial in ensuring financial inclusion and improving mobile banking services for the youth. The Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) analysis in Table 4.10 revealed that mobile banking accessibility ($\beta = 0.34$, $p = 0.027$), usage ($\beta = 0.169$, $p = 0.015$), and digital financial awareness ($\beta = 0.327$, $p = 0.036$) have a significant impact on students' saving behavior. To enhance financial inclusion, policymakers should strengthen national financial literacy programs by integrating financial education into school and university curricula. As indicated in Table 4.9, students require financial education before they can effectively use mobile banking. Government agencies should work with financial institutions to create nationwide financial awareness campaigns aimed at equipping youth with digital banking skills.

In addition, regulators should enforce fair transaction fees and prevent exploitative pricing models that discourage students from using mobile banking for saving. Given that Table 4.5 highlighted

concerns over transaction costs, setting industry-wide standards for reasonable mobile banking fees would encourage greater financial participation. Another critical recommendation is to improve digital financial infrastructure to address the issue of poor internet connectivity, as highlighted in Table 4.9. Governments should invest in expanding mobile banking networks, particularly in rural areas, to ensure that all students can access reliable digital financial services. Furthermore, consumer protection and cybersecurity measures should be strengthened to safeguard users from potential fraud, even though security concerns were not a major barrier (Table 4.9, $M = 2.9145$, $SD = 1.17898$).

Lastly, policymakers should encourage innovation in mobile banking and fintech development by supporting startups and companies that create tailored financial solutions for youth. By fostering a regulatory environment that promotes innovation, governments can drive the expansion of mobile banking services while ensuring financial stability and security.

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APPENDICES

Questionnaire.

Dear Respondents,

I am Jean Claude MURAGIJIMANA, a Master of Business Administration student specializing in Finance at the University of Lay Adventists Of Kigali (UNILAK). I am conducting research titled “**Effects of mobile banking on personal saving trends of youth in Rwanda: a study of mobile banking among university of Rwanda students in Huye campus (2021-2024).**” The questions in this questionnaire are designed to gather information crucial to my academic research. I kindly request your support by providing thoughtful responses to the questionnaire. Please be assured that all information collected will be treated with the utmost confidentiality and will strictly be used for the stated purpose. Thank you for your valuable contribution!

Section A. Identification of the respondent

1. **Gender:** Male Female
2. **Marital status:** Single Married Widow
3. **Level of education:**
Undergraduate
Post –graduate
3. **Age:** 18-24 25-29 30-35

Other (please specify _____)

Please indicate your level of agreement with each statement by choosing one of the following options: **5 – Strongly Agree, 4 – Agree, 3 – Neutral, 2 – Disagree, 1 – Strongly Disagree**

Section B: Mobile Banking Usage

1. Accessibility of Mobile Banking Services

S/N	Statements	5	4	3	2	1
1	It is easy to open a mobile banking account.					
2	Mobile banking services are easily accessible on my mobile device.					
3	There are sufficient mobile banking agents and ATMs near my location.					
4	I do not have trouble when accessing my mobile banking account.					
5	I can easily perform transactions anytime and anywhere.					
	2. Usage of Mobile Banking Services	5	4	3	2	1
1	I frequently use mobile banking services to manage my finances.					
2	I use mobile banking to check account balances and transaction history.					
3	Mobile banking helps me manage my expenses more effectively.					
	3. Digital Financial Literacy	5	4	3	2	1
1	I am aware of the various mobile banking features available.					
2	I have received financial education on how to use mobile banking effectively.					
3	I feel confident using mobile banking applications and services.					
4	I understand mobile banking security measures and fraud prevention.					
5	Digital financial literacy helps me make better saving decisions.					
	4. Affordability of Mobile Banking Services	5	4	3	2	1
1	Mobile banking services are affordable for students.					
2	Transaction fees for mobile banking are reasonable.					
3	The cost of internet and mobile data does not hinder my mobile banking usage.					
4	I prefer mobile banking to traditional banking due to its affordability.					

Section C: Personal Saving Trends

	5. Saving Accessibility	5	4	3	2	1

1	Mobile banking makes it easy for me to open and manage a savings account.					
2	Depositing money into my savings account is convenient with mobile banking.					
3	I can withdraw my savings easily using mobile banking when needed.					
4	Mobile banking offers me better access to saving options compared to traditional banking.					
5	I regularly check my savings balance using mobile banking.					
	6. Saving Motivation	5	4	3	2	1
1	The interest rates on mobile savings accounts motivate me to save more.					
2	I use mobile banking to set and track my financial goals.					
3	Mobile banking allows me to save money more conveniently than cash savings.					
4	I am encouraged to save because of mobile banking incentives or promotions.					
5	Mobile banking helps me develop better financial discipline.					
	7. Saving Outcomes					
1	I am satisfied with the savings services provided by mobile banking.					
2	My savings have increased since I started using mobile banking.					
3	Mobile banking allows me to save small amounts frequently.					
4	I have been able to achieve my financial goals through mobile savings.					
	Section D: Challenges of Mobile Banking for Savings	5	4	3	2	1
1	I experience difficulties accessing mobile banking services.					
2	Transaction fees discourage me from using mobile savings.					
3	Poor internet connectivity affects my mobile banking transactions.					
4	I do not trust mobile banking security.					
5	I need more financial education to use mobile banking effectively.					